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Improving Prognostic Moist Turbulence Parameterization with Machine Learning and Software Design

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Abstract

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The primary result of this work is that concepts from software design and machine learning may be used to improve moist turbulence parameterization in weather and climate models. We have seen relatively slow improvement of moist turbulence parameterization in past decades, and explore a radically different approach to parameterization involving machine learning. The core of the approach is to rely on a trusted source of training data, such as high-resolution models or reanalysis, to be used to train a machine learning algorithm to perform the closures normally defined by conventional parameterization.

The Python packages `symp1` (System for Modelling Planets) and `climt` (Climate Modeling and Diagnostics Toolkit) are introduced. These packages are an attempt to rethink climate modelling frameworks from the ground up. The result defines expressive data structures that enforce software design best practices. It allows scientists to easily and reliably combine model components to represent the climate system at a desired level of complexity and enables users to fully understand what the model is doing.

Random forest and polynomial regression are used as an alternate closure assumption in a higher-order turbulence closure scheme trained for use over the summertime Northeast Pacific stratocumulus to trade cumulus transition region. While the machine learning closures better match high-resolution model data over withheld validation samples compared to a state-of-

the-art higher-order turbulence closure scheme, the resulting model is unstable when used prognostically.

Within a first-order closure framework, an artificial neural network is trained to reproduce thermodynamic tendencies and boundary layer properties from ERA5 Hires reanalysis data over the summertime Northeast Pacific stratocumulus to trade cumulus transition region. The network is trained prognostically using 7-day forecasts rather than using diagnosed instantaneous tendencies alone. The resulting model, Machine Assisted Reanalysis Boundary Layer Emulation (MARBLE), skillfully reproduces the boundary layer structure and cloud properties of the reanalysis data in 7-day single-column prognostic simulations over withheld testing periods. Radiative heating profiles are well-simulated, and the mean climatology and variability of the stratocumulus to cumulus transition are accurately reproduced. MARBLE more closely tracks the reanalysis than does a comparable configuration of the underlying forecast model. Similar results are obtained over the Southern Great Plains.

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GLOSSARY

ACTIVATION FUNCTION: A scalar function applied to the total input activity of a neuron in a neural network to determine the output activity of that neuron.

BOOTSTRAP SAMPLE: A sample of a dataset which is of the same size as the original dataset, where samples are randomly selected with replacement. This will usually mean some samples are selected multiple times, and other samples are not selected at all.

FEATURE: An input or output variable of a predictive machine learning algorithm

FRAMEWORK: A defined system of code which can be selectively modified to create specific applications. A framework provides a standard way to design and build software. Contrast to toolkit.

HYPERPARAMETER: Modifiable properties of the machine learning algorithm, which can be modified between successive training runs of a model. For example, the number of neurons used in a layer of a neural network.

L_1 REGULARIZATION: Including a term proportional to the sum of the absolute values of the weights of the machine learning model in the loss function that is minimized. This encourages values of 0 for less relevant weights.

L_2 REGULARIZATION: Including a term proportional to the sum of the squared values of the weights of the machine learning model in the loss function that is minimized. This discourages large values of weights which might otherwise be used to over-fit the training data.

LEARNING RATE: A value used to scale the magnitude of the updates to model weights performed at each training iteration.

LOSS: a measure of model performance which is minimized in the course of training the model.

NEURAL NETWORK: A machine learning algorithm composed of layers of neurons with connectivity weights, followed by a nonlinear activation function.

OVERFITTING: when a model matches the training data too closely, causing it to perform poorly on unseen data

PARAMETER: Model variables that are determined automatically in the course of training a machine learning algorithm using training data.

RANDOM FOREST: A machine learning algorithm that uses an ensemble of decision trees to produce a prediction.

REGULARIZATION: A penalty on model complexity included in the loss function to prevent overfitting

SUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING: A model which produces a mapping from inputs to outputs. For example, a random forest.

TESTING DATASET: Subset of data used to test a model after hyperparameters have been optimized using the validation dataset.

TOOLKIT: A collection of code producing functionality to be used by applications. Contrast to framework.

TRAINING DATASET: Subset of data used to train a model.

UNSUPERVISED MACHINE LEARNING: A model which finds patterns in a dataset, such as a lower dimensional representation of that dataset. For example, principal component analysis.

VALIDATION DATASET: Subset of data used to optimize model hyperparameters by modifying those parameters to minimize the model loss on the validation data, when trained using the training data.

DEDICATION

to Mom

PREFACE

The tendency in research is to compartmentalize, and narrow one's focus of expertise to a small area. A scientist named Konrad Lorenz once said "Scientists are people who know more and more about less and less, until they know everything about nothing". Breadth of research is achieved through the breadth of researchers. A danger of this approach is that one can develop tunnel vision, and fail to see the broader picture or, as is central to this dissertation, learn lessons from other areas of expertise.

The most useful class I ever took as an undergraduate physics student was *Introduction to Computer Programming*, taught by the Computer Science department. This wasn't because I learned topics in that class which I couldn't learn on my own or weren't presented in the wiki we were given in place of a programming course through the Physics department. It was because computer scientists think about programming in a fundamentally different way than physical scientists, and place their focus on a different set of issues. These same issues come up in scientific fields, but are brushed aside as non-critical issues until one day a researcher is trying to interpret a model output "OL1" with description "something" and units of "whoknows".

Global atmospheric models, such as weather and climate models, are by and large exceedingly difficult to read and work with from a software design standpoint. Variable names are often non-descriptive and undocumented. Modules are tightly coupled without well-defined or documented interfaces. Unit tests are rare. These problems make it challenging to bring new scientists in to add new components to models, port components between models, or make changes to model code.

These challenges were the motivation for the System for Modeling Planets (Sympl) frame-

work presented in Chapter 2. This framework is designed to either encourage or force scientists to adopt good coding practices. Modularity is ensured by definition of individual components with clear interfaces that can be combined to make a model. Documentation must be written for components, because that documentation is directly used by the code itself. These are considerations that are not normally on the radar when writing new atmospheric model code.

Similarly, the most useful conference I have ever been to was PyCon 2016 in Portland, Oregon. Attending that conference made me think about machine learning and its application in new ways I wouldn't have been exposed to by listening to another physical scientist. When I first read about higher-order turbulence closure and CLUBB (discussed in Chapter 3), machine learning came quickly to mind as a possible approach because of my recent attendance at this conference. This insight was the base on which my work as a doctoral student was built. I am grateful to Chris that, following promising initial results, he allowed me to explore this idea in my doctoral research. I hope you enjoy reading through my journey in this field as much as I enjoyed exploring it.

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I would like to thank the organizers of the 2016 PyCon in Portland, Oregon for providing

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Stratocumulus clouds cover over one-fifth of Earth’s surface in the annual mean [58]. These clouds strongly reflect incoming shortwave radiation and have little effect on outgoing longwave radiation, resulting in a strong cooling radiative effect on Earth’s energy balance [10, 60]. Small changes in stratocumulus cover and thickness are sufficient to produce radiative effects comparable to the effects associated with increasing greenhouse gases [52]. Thus, climate model behavior in subtropical stratocumulus to cumulus transition regions such as the Northeast Pacific is critical in representing Earth’s energy balance and cloud feedbacks on climate.

Significant biases and challenges persist in the representation of stratocumulus clouds in climate models (e.g. Hannay et al. [24], Medeiros et al. [38], Lin et al. [36], Dal Gesso et al. [13]). Traditional parameterizations have difficulty representing stratocumulus and their transition to cumulus, because the stratocumulus layer is thin, capped by a sharp inversion, and maintained by turbulent eddies unresolved at the grid scale of climate models. These eddies are strongly influenced by the clouds and their radiative effects, and may have a complex vertical structure. Turbulent entrainment through the sharp inversion is particularly important but subject to numerical errors as well as representational uncertainties.

The complexity of this problem and the relatively slow improvement of climate model simulations of these cloudy boundary layers suggests the exploration of radically different parameterization approaches, such as the use of machine learning to holistically represent the combined effect of all of the interacting processes.

A contributor to the slow improvement of climate model simulations is the difficulty involved in understanding and modifying their code bases. Tight coupling, opaquely named

variables, and lack of documentation is common in climate model development. In Chapter 2, published as Monteiro et al. [39], we introduce the System for Modeling Planets (Sympl) framework that is meant to rectify some of these issues. Along with the Climate Modeling Toolkit (CliMT (also presented), or using user-defined components, this framework can be used to write clear, self-documenting climate models. In later chapters, this toolkit is used to run new machine learning parameterizations in Python single column models.

Using Sympl to aid development, the problem of moist turbulence parameterization and cloud representation in atmospheric models is tackled in Chapter 3. Here a new higher-order turbulence closure called Closing Higher Orders with a Machine Learning Parameterization (CHOMP) is presented, trained on a relatively small dataset of high-resolution model output. This is compared with the existing Cloudy Layers Unified By Binormals (CLUBB) model. While we show significant improvement over CLUBB in a diagnostic sense, we are unable to produce a stable prognostic model using CHOMP, for reasons discussed in this chapter.

The lessons learned in creating CHOMP bring us forward to a new machine learning moist turbulence parameterization called Machine Assisted Boundary Layer Emulation (MARBLE). In Chapter 4, this model is presented and evaluated over the Northeast Pacific stratocumulus to cumulus transition region. With a significantly larger reanalysis dataset, we are able to produce a single-column model that out-performs the forecast model used to create the reanalysis product. The results of Chapter 4 have been submitted for publication by McGibbon and Bretherton in *Geophys. Res. Lett.*. MARBLE is further assessed over land in the Southern Great Plains (SGP) in Chapter 5.

In the concluding remarks in Chapter 6, we discuss next steps. CHOMP is reassessed in light of the lessons learned in developing MARBLE. We also explore how machine learning parameterizations might be used in global models, as opposed to in a single-column setting.

Chapter 2

MODEL DESIGN AND SYMPL

The climate is a complex system composed of interacting subsystems (atmosphere, ocean, cryosphere, biosphere, chemosphere), each encompassing a broad range of physical and chemical processes with space and time scales spanning many orders of magnitude. Modelling and understanding the climate system in its entirety is a grand scientific and technological challenge. An increasingly recognised strategy for tackling this challenge is to build a hierarchy of models of varying complexity. Simpler models are more amenable to in-depth analysis and understanding; the insight gained from these simpler models can then be used to understand more complicated models, and so on [25]. Specifying which particular models should occupy each rung in such a hierarchy is necessarily a matter of subjective choice, and the questions of how to create a hierarchy and what models are desirable in a canonical hierarchy has generated extensive discussions [29]. Our purpose here is to present a modelling framework that enables climate scientists to easily and transparently traverse the specific model hierarchy suiting their needs.

Designing and building a framework that facilitates traversing this hierarchy remains a challenge. The lack of flexibility of existing climate models forces scientists to spend a lot of time reading and modifying code to construct alternative model versions that should in principle be straightforward to build. Most modelling frameworks simply provide code to exchange information between different physical domains such as atmosphere and ocean (See [54, 56] for a survey of modelling frameworks), with each physical domain being represented by a monolithic block of code. It was only with the advent a new generation of frameworks like the Earth System Modelling Framework (ESMF) [15, 54] that fine-grained control over the components that constitute a climate model was made possible. For instance, ESMF allows

configuring components as trees, where the leaf nodes could represent physical processes such as radiation and the root of the tree could represent a physical domain such as the atmosphere. Such a hierarchical ordering of physical processes is also present in Python based modelling packages – previous versions of `climt` and `climlab` (<https://github.com/brian-rose/climlab>) allow building models in a manner similar to ESMF. However, the norm continues to be that climate model composition is configured by namelist variables and boolean flags in the code rather than framework-based approaches (like the component trees that ESMF allows).

Another emerging concern in the scientific community is that of reproducibility of research [43]. While publicly available climate models do provide validated configurations that are in principle completely reproducible, climate scientists routinely need to make changes to the code that are hard to document (or understand). Short of sharing a copy of the entire code base, such modifications makes it difficult to reproduce simulations. While some level of code manipulation is inescapable, we note from our own experience and from reading about such modifications in the literature that most of them follow set patterns that could easily be provided by modelling frameworks themselves.

In this paper we present a new modelling framework, `symp1`, and a model toolkit, `climt`. While `symp1` focuses on providing a model framework, a rich taxonomy of components, and model agnostic configuration options, `climt` focuses on providing a broad array of physical components to allow users to build scientifically useful models. `climt` also provides model dependent configuration options and helper functions to create an initial model state as required by the components.

`symp1` and `climt` allow finer grained control over the composition of the model, with individual components representing physical processes (such as radiation, convection, etc.) rather than physical domains. Attempting to model the climate system at the physical process level has its own challenges which we attempt to solve in these packages. Initiatives to build frameworks to traverse the hierarchy between highly idealised models to full scale GCMs (general circulation models) do exist [20, 57], but we believe the definition of a clear

set of classes to represent the physical process level of the model to be unique.

`symp1` and `climt` allow writing models that are easy to use and facilitate reproducibility of simulations. Both these packages are subject to ongoing development, but have reached a level of maturity that makes it worthwhile to document them here. In section 2.1, we present a series of models written using `symp1` and `climt` which illustrate the construction of a model hierarchy. In section 2.2 we describe some challenges that modelling frameworks have to solve (in the context of the above examples when possible) and discuss how `symp1` and `climt` address these challenges. We then discuss in more detail the interfaces of `symp1` (section 2.4) and `climt` (section 2.5). In section 2.6 we present some benchmark calculations, and conclude with a discussion of developments planned in the future.

2.1 `symp1` and `climt` in action

To illustrate the advantages of the fine-grained control that `symp1` and `climt` offer, we consider a series of examples starting with a diagnostic radiative calculation and ending with an idealised three dimensional atmospheric general circulation model.

Figure 2.1 shows the script required to calculate the heating tendencies from a longwave radiative transfer component [11]. A detailed explanation of the script follows:

- **Line 1:** Import the `climt` package.
- **Line 4:** Instantiate a radiative transfer component.
- **Line 7:** Create a state dictionary which contains all the quantities required as inputs by the radiative transfer component.
- **Line 9:** Calculate the heating rate (available in `tendencies` and any associated diagnostics such as the radiative fluxes (available in `diagnostics`)).

In Figure 2.1, we have used the default values for quantities in `model_state`, which corresponds to an isothermal atmosphere.

```

1  import climt
2
3  # Create component
4  radiation = climt.RRTMGLongwave()
5
6  # Create model state
7  model_state = climt.get_default_state([radiation])
8
9  tendencies, diagnostics = radiation(model_state)

```

Figure 2.1: A Python script that calculates the heating tendencies and associated diagnostics from a longwave radiative transfer component. See the text for a detailed description.

This example, though seemingly simple, is remarkable because of the ease with which such a diagnostic calculation can be performed. Traditionally, such a calculation would involve writing a Fortran “driver”, compiling it with the radiative transfer library, writing the output to a file, and then reading the output file into a suitable environment for further analysis. The ease of use illustrated in the above example is a direct result of the fine-grained control that `symp1` and `climt` allow – individual components can be configured and run (interactively, if desired) without having to compile them with a driver file. To summarise, *components*, not models, are first class entities within the `symp1` framework.

It is worth examining this example in greater detail, since it highlights some important features of `symp1` and `climt` that we will look at closely in subsequent sections. The component called `radiation` is an implementation of the `symp1` entity called `TendencyComponent`, which is a template for components which calculate tendencies of a quantity (air temperature in this case) based on quantities in a state dictionary. We will encounter other kinds of components in subsequent examples.

Figure 2.2 builds upon the previous example to create a model that includes both radiation and convection, steps the state quantities forward in time, and writes the output to a file. The changes from the previous script are as follows:

```

1  from sympy import (
2      AdamsBashforth, NetCDFMonitor)
3  import climt
4  from datetime import timedelta
5
6  # Define model timestep in minutes
7  model_timestep = timedelta(minutes=1)
8
9  # Create components
10 radiation = climt.RRTMGLongwave()
11 convection = climt.EmanuelConvection()
12 boundary_layer = climt.SimplePhysics()
13
14 # Create model state
15 model_state = climt.get_default_state(
16     [radiation, convection, boundary_layer])
17
18 # Create integrator
19 time_stepper = AdamsBashforth(
20     [radiation, convection])
21
22 # Create monitor
23 monitor = NetCDFMonitor('radiative_convective.nc')
24
25 # step model forward
26 for step in range(10):
27     bl_diagnostics, bl_new_state = boundary_layer(
28         model_state, model_timestep)
29     model_state.update(bl_diagnostics)
30     model_state.update(bl_new_state)
31
32     diagnostics, new_state = time_stepper(
33         model_state, model_timestep)
34     model_state.update(diagnostics)
35     monitor.store(model_state)
36     model_state.update(new_state)
37     model_state['time'] += model_timestep

```

Figure 2.2: A Python script which calculates the radiative-convective equilibrium temperature of an atmospheric column for a fixed surface temperature. See the text for a detailed description.

- **Line 7:** Define the model time step using `timedelta` from the `datetime` library, which is part of any Python distribution.
- **Line 21:** Create a time integrator which steps the model state forward in time, using tendencies generated by the radiation and convection components. The integrator chosen is an instance of the `symp1 Stepper` class which implements a variety of Adams-Bashforth schemes.
- **Line 24:** Create a “monitor” component which writes the model state to a netCDF file.
- **Lines 27-37:** The boundary layer component provides new values of model quantities, which are used to update the model state. The time integrator incorporates the tendencies due to radiation and convection and provides new values for the model state as well. The current model state is updated with diagnostics and written to a netCDF file. The model state is then updated with the new model quantities to prepare for the next iteration.

This example illustrates how to piece together a radiative-convective equilibrium (RCE) model from different kinds of `symp1` components. This example also moves up the model hierarchy, away from static diagnostic calculations to a model which evolves in time. It is worth noting that the first half of the example which creates components and a model state remains identical to the procedure followed in the previous example. This example shows two notable features of the design of `symp1` and `clint` – One, individual components can step the model state forward themselves and Two, the model integrator is a separate entity in itself which can be replaced easily (to use more stable integration schemes, for example). These features are in keeping with our goal of capturing the diversity of model components – some of which produce tendencies, and others that produce new state quantities – and allowing the user fine-grained control over model configuration.

This example also illustrates how `symp1`'s design provides a clear understanding of the model to users. Configuring the model consists of modifying a run script which is meant to be entirely legible to the user. By reading the run script, one can see exactly which model components are being used, how the state is initialised, what configuration options are being passed to which components, what time integration scheme is used on which components, the order in which components are being called, and the point within the integration where the state is being output to a file.

Figure 2.3 presents the next step in the hierarchy from Fig. 2.2, creating a moist atmospheric general circulation model (AGCM) in an aqua-planet configuration with a prescribed sea surface temperature. The default surface temperature is horizontally uniform, but we omit prescribing a realistic temperature distribution for purposes of comparison with Fig. 2.2. The main differences from the previous example are:

- **Line 14:** The boundary layer component is wrapped to output tendencies instead of a new state. This wrapper is required since the spectral dynamical core must apply tendencies to most quantities in spectral space for numerical reasons.
- **Line 18:** The spectral dynamical core is used as the time stepper instead of the Adams-Bashforth scheme used previously.
- **Lines 22 and 25:** Since the model now has three dimensions, we require a grid describing the latitudes, longitudes as well. Line 18 creates a model grid, and the default model state created in Line 21 uses this grid to create an appropriate three dimensional state.

A remarkable fact about this example is that it is only one line longer than the previous example. Intuitively, this seems appropriate – an AGCM can be thought of as a collection of radiative-convective columns which communicate with each other via the dynamical core. However, in most modelling frameworks the intuitive picture of the transition from an RCE to an AGCM does not easily translate to code. This plug-and-play behaviour is a direct

```

1  from sympl import (
2      TimeDifferencingWrapper, NetCDFMonitor)
3  import climt
4  from datetime import timedelta
5
6  # Define model timestep in minutes
7  model_timestep = timedelta(minutes=1)
8
9  # Create Components
10 radiation = climt.RRTMGLongwave()
11 convection = climt.EmanuelConvection()
12 boundary_layer = TimeDifferencingWrapper(
13     climt.SimplePhysics())
14 time_stepper = GFSDynamicalCore(
15     [radiation, convection, boundary_layer])
16
17 # Create model grid
18 model_grid = climt.get_grid(nx=64, ny=64, nz=28)
19
20 # Create model state
21 model_state = climt.get_default_state(
22     [time_stepper], grid_state=model_grid)
23
24 # Create monitor
25 monitor = NetCDFMonitor('moist_agcm.nc')
26
27 # step model forward
28 for step in range(10):
29     diagnostics, new_state = time_stepper(
30         model_state, model_timestep)
31     model_state.update(diagnostics)
32     monitor.store(model_state)
33     model_state.update(new_state)
34     model_state['time'] += model_timestep

```

Figure 2.3: A Python script which creates an idealised moist atmospheric general circulation model. See text for a detailed description.

consequence of the modularity of individual `symp1` components and the fact that all components of a similar kind (`AdamsBashforth` and `GFSDynamicalCore` in this case) implement the same interface, making it possible to reuse almost the entire model script from the RCE case. In this way, `symp1` and `climt` allow constructing models in such a way that a change that intuitively seems small also translates to a code change that is small.

In this following section, we look at detail at the design decisions that allow for the construction of a model hierarchy as described in the three examples in this section.

2.2 Design considerations and choices

In this paper we distinguish between modelling frameworks, model toolkits, and models themselves. A framework (such as `symp1`) consists of abstractions of "infrastructure" code that allow the creation of climate models. A framework creates rules one must follow, but by doing so ensures models using the framework are easier to write, understand, and combine with one another. A toolkit (such as `climt`) implements those abstractions for concrete physical processes, and may provide additional functionality that is not covered by the framework. A model itself (such as in Figures 2.2 and 2.3) is written using components that may come from a toolkit which follows the guidelines of the framework.

Modelling frameworks should enable scientists to intuitively combine model components and create an appropriately complex model for the scientific question at hand. The user should also be able to specify details such as the order in which components are called and the time stepping schemes used. Model toolkits should provide a wide variety of components that enable users to write a model appropriate to the question at hand. Toolkits should also maintain a list of quantities and numerical grids that are required by the components it provides to facilitate creating model arrays. It is also desirable that the process of creating a model is fairly easy to understand and that the model code be self-documenting to eliminate the need to write additional documentation whenever possible.

2.2.1 *Component diversity*

One of the major aims of `symp1` and `climt` is to allow fine-grained control over the processes that constitute an Earth system model. In currently available modelling frameworks, the integration of scientific code (or model components) and the modelling framework happens at the physical domain level – atmosphere, ocean, land and so on. The processes that operate within each physical domain (fluid dynamics, radiation, convection etc.) are not accessible in a systematic manner, and their code becomes tightly coupled and difficult to modify. For example, changing the radiation code in an atmospheric model is typically harder than changing the kind of ocean the atmosphere is coupled to (slab, dynamical, etc.). Tight coupling of code at the process level can make these models more efficient, but at the cost of scientist efficiency, as the code is significantly less flexible and have undocumented and complicated interfaces between components.

Furthermore, the fact that certain process level components are written to work only with certain other components demands an “architectural unity” [45] which might also encourage tight integration of model components. Within `symp1`, it may still be the case that two components are incompatible with one another (for example, using different thermodynamic quantities), but because their interfaces are clearly defined, it is easier to couple these components (for example, by converting thermodynamic quantities using an additional component). Other incompatibilities are handled automatically. For example, `symp1` automatically ensures components which use different units or dimension orderings can be used alongside one another.

If we allow for configuration at the process level, we are then faced with model components which behave quite differently: Some components (like radiation) return tendencies, while others (like large scale condensation) return a new value of a physical quantity. `symp1` provides a set of component classes that is comprehensive enough to capture the diversity of component behaviours.

An example of a `symp1` component is depicted in Fig. 2.4. `input_properties` and

```

1 class PrescribedHeating(TendencyComponent):
2
3     input_properties = {
4         'latitude': {
5             'dims': ['*'],
6             'units': 'degrees_N',
7         },
8         'longitude': {
9             'dims': ['*'],
10            'units': 'degrees_E',
11        },
12        'air_pressure': {
13            'dims': ['mid_levels', '*'],
14            'units': 'Pa',
15        },
16    }
17
18    diagnostic_properties = {}
19
20    tendency_properties = {
21        'air_temperature': {
22            'dims': ['mid_levels', '*'],
23            'units': 'degK s^-1',
24        }
25    }
26
27    def __init__(self, forcing_filename, **kwargs):
28        [...]
29        super(PrescribedHeating, self).__init__(**kwargs)
30
31    def array_call(self, state):
32        [...]

```

Figure 2.4: The general code layout for a sympl component.

`tendency_properties` are ‘property’ attributes containing details of the required inputs and returned outputs, tendencies or diagnostics. Here, the input is a quantity `air_temperature` whose horizontal dimensions are `latitude`, `longitude` and whose values in the vertical are defined at model mid-levels. The units are specified for each quantity. The `array_call` method will be called by `symp1` with numpy arrays that are automatically extracted from the model state to satisfy the input property specifications. It is written to return numpy arrays as output which satisfy its tendency and diagnostic property specifications. The `__call__` method which is called, for example, in Line 9 of Fig. 2.1, is implemented by the base `symp1` classes. This method encapsulates the boilerplate code of performing consistency checks on the model state, extracting numpy arrays with the correct units and shape, and creating a new state dictionary from the arrays returned by `array_call`.

Dimension and unit requirements in `symp1` are not restrictions on the inputs, but rather describe the internal representation used by the component. `symp1` will automatically convert the input state to satisfy these requirements, and raise an exception if that is not possible. In this way, the property dictionaries act as self-documenting code, which both documents the component interface and is used to convert input arrays to the desired dimension ordering and units for the component.

As a `TendencyComponent` (discussed in Section 2.4), this component outputs tendencies of a quantity `air_temperature`. The `array_call()` method accepts a dictionary containing just the `numpy` arrays extracted from the model state with the correct units and dimensions and returns the temperature tendency as specified in the component properties.

Since components in `symp1` and `climt` are first class entities, they are not dependent on any other code for execution – Fig. 2.1 shows how to interact solely with a radiative component without the need for an integrator or any other entity. This behaviour serves an important educational purpose and facilitates diagnostic calculations made very often during research.

2.2.2 Model configuration

Together, `symp1` and `climt` allow a natural way of configuring various aspects of a climate model listed below:

- Physical configuration (toolkit agnostic): the physical constants required by the model components.
- Algorithmic configuration (toolkit specific): the “tunable” parameters which modify the behaviour of the algorithm which represent physical processes – for example, the entrainment coefficient in a convective parameterisation.
- Interfacial configuration (toolkit agnostic): Modifications applied to inputs and outputs at the interface of a component, further described below.
- Memory and Computing resource configuration (toolkit specific): The layout of arrays used by the model and the distribution of the model components over the available number of processors and co-processors.
- Compositional configuration (toolkit specific): The components that compose a model, any dependency between components, the order in which components are executed all need to be described.

Figure 2.5 shows types of configuration information and where such configuration lies `climt/symp1` and in traditional climate models. In contrast to `symp1` where all configuration passes through a readable run script, the sheer variety of locations where the configuration resides in traditional models makes it hard to keep track of what configuration information has changed, and how configuration changes affect model runs. This makes it daunting for beginners to write models. Model configuration using `symp1` and `climt` is highly centralised and easily accessible - all configuration passes through the model run script, which is written

to be readable and accessible to model users. Such centralised configuration reduces errors arising due to misconfiguration of the model.

While most of the configuration elements listed above are familiar, interfacial configuration is mostly unheard of and usually applied in a non-systematic manner within climate models. The `TimeDifferencingWrapper` used in line 14 of Figure 2.3 is an example of interfacial configuration of a climate model component. There are a variety of interfacial modifications which are commonly applied to components, and can be applied in a consistent manner across components. For instance, model components could

- Normally return a new value rather than a tendency of some physical quantity, but in certain instances a tendency might be desirable (as in Figure 2.3).
- Provide output that is piece-wise constant in time – the output is updated only once every N iterations, and the same value it output for the next $N - 1$ iterations. This behaviour is normally used in radiative transfer codes.
- Scale some of its inputs or outputs by some floating point number. This kind of behaviour is desirable for example in mechanism denial studies.

We can interfacially modify certain behaviours of model components, such as the ones above, by interacting with only the inputs and outputs of scientific components. `sympl` formalises such configuration by providing wrapper objects like `TimeDifferencingWrapper`.

2.3 Model arrays

Model arrays are contained within the `DataArray` abstraction provided by `xarray` [28] rather than the more low-level `numpy` array. `DataArrays` are an abstraction over `numpy` arrays with a more natural fit to climate data by providing labeled dimensions and metadata storage capabilities.

`sympl`'s `DataArray` object is a subclass of the `xarray` `DataArray` that provides units handling and conversion and will be described subsequently. This exposes the powerful

Figure 2.5: The variety of configuration options in a climate model and in the `sympl-climt` framework. The coloured boxes indicate the type of configuration and the white boxes parts of the model code base. Arrows from the coloured to the white boxes indicate the part of the code base that is typically responsible for the configuration from which the arrow originates. A particular type of configuration could exist in two different parts of the code base: such a situation is indicated by multiple arrows terminating at all the relevant white boxes. Note that not every climate model uses all configuration options. The starred box on the `sympl+climt` side indicates functionality that is not yet implemented.

analysis capabilities of `xarray`, allowing users to build an end-to-end pipeline entirely within Python, from simulation to data analysis and generation of publication-ready figures.

Since low-level array operations using `numpy` and `xarray` are fairly simple, especially changing coordinate ordering and C/Fortran memory ordering, `climt` only provides guidelines for memory layout of arrays. However, changing the ordering of dimensions in memory will incur the performance penalty of copying the array if the model calls compiled code.

In the interest of readability of component and model code, `symp1` strongly encourages and `climt` makes use of descriptive names for model quantities, adhering to the CF conventions¹ when possible. Most pre-defined quantities in `climt` use names derived from the CF conventions. One additional suffix that we found necessary to use was `on_interface_levels` to distinguish between quantities defined on the interfaces and mid-levels of the vertical grid. For example `air_temperature` refers to the air temperature defined at the vertical grid centre, whereas `air_temperature_on_interface_levels` refers to the same quantity defined at the vertical grid edges. This convention is only a requirement within the model state. Within an individual component, shorter names can be used for variables representing quantities. This shorter name is also contained in the property dictionary of the component, serving as documentation for the meaning of that shorter variable name.

2.3.1 Modelling language

Python was used as the language to write the framework. Python as a language and the Python ecosystem have a number of desirable features, all of which were taken advantage of during the development of `symp1` and `climt`:

- Earlier versions of `climt` were written in Python, which gave the authors an idea of the convenience and flexibility it afforded. In particular, the object-oriented capabilities of Python provide a straightforward way to represent the component based architecture adopted by almost all climate modelling frameworks.

¹ <http://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-standard-names/48/build/cf-standard-name-table.html>

- Scientific libraries within the Python ecosystem now offer acceptable performance for computationally intensive operations typically used in climate models.
- The Python ecosystem includes many libraries which can be useful in developing climate models. Examples include machine learning, graphics and web services libraries.
- Python’s ability to act as a glue language allows interfacing with the large number of libraries for climate modelling already available in Fortran.
- Tools available in the Python ecosystem like `jupyter`, `pytest` and `sphinx` which enable writing reproducible workflows and code that is well documented and tested.

2.4 `symp1` – *Design and programming interface*

`symp1` conceives of a climate model as a state that is continuously updated by various components. `symp1`’s taxonomy consists of seven kinds of components. Four of these component types are used to represent physical processes and the remaining represent other functionality required to build and run models.

- `TendencyComponent` objects like `RRTMGLongwave` in Fig. 2.1 which take the model state as input and returns tendencies of quantities and values of quantities defined at the time of the input state.
- `Stepper` components like `SimplePhysics` in Fig. 2.2 which take the model state and a timestep as input and returns values of quantities defined at a new time (after the timestep) and optionally diagnostic values of quantities defined at the time of the input state. These are implicit as they define the target model state in terms of the target model state (e.g. that the target state is not supersaturated).
- `DiagnosticComponent` objects which take the model state as input and return quantities defined at the time of the input state as output.

- `ImplicitTendencyComponent` objects like `EmanuelConvection` in Fig. 2.2 which return tendencies, but require the model timestep to produce these tendencies. This is required when the tendencies are defined in terms of the target model state, as is often done in convection schemes or flux limiters. These should generally be written as `Stepper` components which can later be wrapped into `ImplicitTendencyComponent` objects if needed (such as with `SimplePhysics` in line 14 of Fig. 2.3).
- `TendencyStepper` components like `AdamsBashforth` in Fig. 2.2 which contain a set of `TendencyComponent` objects and use the tendencies they output to integrate the model state forward in time.
- `Monitor` components like `NetCDFMonitor` in Fig. 2.2 which provide a `store` method which takes the model state as input and “stores” it. The implementation of this method is left to the user, and currently is used for NetCDF output and plotting.
- `Wrapper` components like `TimeDifferencingWrapper` in Fig. 2.3 which contain other `symp1` components and modify the inputs passed to or outputs generated by the ‘wrapped’ component.

Schematics of how the above components interact with the model state are presented in Figure 2.6. In all figures, dark green boxes denote components, light green boxes denote optional wrappers, orange boxes indicate the state dictionary at different times and purple boxes indicate tendencies and diagnostics generated by components. The converging arrows at a summation symbol (plus sign inscribed within a circle) denotes updating the state dictionary (orange) to include output (purple) quantities. Examples of wrapper placements are not exhaustive and meant only as examples.

A `DiagnosticComponent` object (Panel a) is very simple, producing diagnostic quantities that are inserted or updated in the current model state. `Monitor` objects (Panel b) take in the model state and perform some action using it. Slightly more complicated is the `Stepper` object (Panel c), which steps the model state forward in time. In addition to

producing a new state, it can produce diagnostic quantities which are inserted or updated in the current model state. Panel d is the most complex, depicting how `TendencyComponent` objects are used with a `TendencyStepper` to update the model state. Once created, a `TendencyStepper` behaves exactly like an `Stepper` object. Internally, it provides the input state to the `TendencyComponent` objects to compute tendencies, and uses those tendencies according to its time stepping scheme to evolve the model state forward in time. The `TendencyStepper` provides the same model state to all `TendencyComponent` objects it contains and sums the tendencies before stepping forward in time (See Fig. 2.6d). Using other time marching algorithms such as sequential tendency or sequential update splitting [16] will require users to implement their own `TendencyStepper` object, or to call several `Stepper` and `TendencyStepper` components in sequence.

As mentioned previously, wrapper components contain a "wrapped" component and modify the inputs or outputs, changing how the component appears to behave. Currently, `symp1` has the following wrappers:

- `TimeDifferencingWrapper` creates tendencies from the output of an `Stepper` component by first order differencing. This creates an `ImplicitTendencyComponent` from an `Stepper` component, which is required when using spectral methods.
- `UpdateFrequencyWrapper` calls a wrapped `TendencyComponent` only after the user-specified time interval has elapsed, and until then outputs the previously returned value. In effect, this creates a piecewise constant output tendency which can reduce the computational load during a simulation. This is often used on radiation schemes.
- `ScalingWrapper` scales the inputs passed into the wrapped component and the outputs (new state, tendency or diagnostic) returned by the component.

This taxonomy of components is larger than those typically used in modelling frameworks. For example, ESMF only considers two kinds of components – Gridded and Coupler

Figure 2.6: Flow of data for each type of component in `symp1`. The four panels show: **a)** `DiagnosticComponent`, which creates diagnostics (purple box) based on the current state. The current state is updated with the resulting diagnostics, resulting in the updated current state. **b)** `Monitor`, which can “store” the updated current state into some format like `NetCDF` or plots. **c)** `Stepper`, which determines a new state from the current state and a time step, and also diagnostics from the time of the current state which are used to update the current state. The current state could then be passed on to `Monitor` components (see panel **b**). **d)** `TendencyStepper`, which is a special case of `Stepper` initialised with a list of `TendencyComponent` objects (denoted by green boxes within a grey box). It passes the current state on to those `TendencyComponent` objects to compute tendencies and diagnostics, which are used to compute its outputs (generally using a time stepping scheme).

components. However, as discussed previously, this extended taxonomy is required to capture the diversity of components that arise if models are written to be configurable and modular at the process level.

2.4.1 Model State and the `DataArray` abstraction

The model state is a dictionary whose keys are the names of model quantities and values are `symp1` `DataArray` objects. The model state also contains a required keyword `time` whose value is an object that implements the Python `datetime` or `timedelta` interface. `symp1` provides an interface to use the `datetime` objects from the `cftime`² package to support several different calendars, as well as dates not supported by the `numpy datetime64` or built-in `datetime` objects. A schematic of the model state is presented in Fig. 2.7. `symp1` does not put hard restrictions on the name of model quantities, though standardised names should be used to ensure inter-package compatibility. All `DataArray` objects must define a string attribute called `units`, which is used to convert the data contained within to the appropriate units requested by a component. The units conversion is performed internally using the `Pint`³ library. Since the actual contents of the state is dependent on model details, `symp1` assumes that the initialisation of the model state will be done by a model package (such as `climt`, or by the user.

2.4.2 Physical Constants

`symp1` maintains a unit-aware library of constants which can be accessed or modified by model packages and by the user through `get_constant()` and `set_constant()` functions. For example, `planetary_rotation_rate` can be changed with a single function call. The unit handling is important to ensure constants are given to components in the units they each require. For example, the RRTMG radiative transfer code [11], requires physical constants

²<https://github.com/Unidata/cftime>

³<https://pint.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Figure 2.7: The model state as in the `symp1` framework. The state in the orange box contains all the information that is stepped forward in time. Each `DataArray` contains information such as the quantity name, units and dimensions/coordinates.

in CGS units.

For the purposes of logging, physical constants are classified into various categories:

- planetary constants such as rotation rate, acceleration due to gravity.
- physical constants such as the speed of light.
- atmospheric constants such as specific heat of dry air and reference air pressure.
- stellar constants such as stellar irradiance
- condensible constants which refer to the thermodynamic properties of the condensible (in all three phases) in the atmosphere.
- Oceanographic constants such as the reference sea water density.

We chose to keep the constants related to the condensible component of the atmosphere separate to ensure `symp1` is flexible enough to handle general planetary atmospheres. `symp1`

provides a function `set_condensible()` which allows switching all constants related to the condensible. For example `set_condensible('methane')` will replace all condensible constants (such as density of liquid/solid/gaseous phases, latent heat of condensation) to those corresponding to methane, provided such constants are already in the constants dictionary. The default condensible is water, which is currently the only condensible compound for which default values are given by `symp1`.

2.4.3 Modelling using *symp1*

A typical workflow when using a model written using `symp1`, as seen in previous examples such as Fig. 2.2 and Fig. 2.3, might involve the following steps:

1. Initialise model components, providing configuration information.
2. Use `Wrapper` components to modify the behaviour of any components if necessary.
3. Initialise model state which contains all quantities required by the selected components.
4. Use `TendencyStepper` to collect all `TendencyComponent` components into a component that can step the model state forward in time.
5. Begin the model main loop.
6. Call `DiagnosticComponent` to compute any derived quantities from prognostic quantities or provide forcing quantities at a given time step.
7. Call `Stepper` components and get a new state dictionary with the updated model quantities and any diagnostics. Update the initial model state with diagnostics.
8. Call `TendencyStepper` and get a new state dictionary with the updated model quantities and any diagnostics. Update the initial model state with diagnostics.

9. Call any `Monitor` components to store the initial model state (e.g. store to disk, display in real time, send over the network).
10. Increment model time and repeat the model main loop.

2.5 `climt` – *Design and programming interface*

2.5.1 *Model state, quantity dimensions and output dictionaries*

For initialisation, `climt` provides the functions `get_grid()` and `get_default_state()`. `get_grid()` creates quantities that define the grid such as latitude, longitude, and air pressure. `get_default_state()` accepts a list of components and optionally a state with grid quantities and creates a state dictionary which satisfies the input requirements for those components. Default values of each model quantity are defined centrally in `climt`. The default values provided are scientifically meaningful, and can be used without modification for certain simulations.

2.5.2 *Model Composition*

Currently, the creation of the model and running the simulation loop is done by hand, which provides better understanding of what the model is doing but increases the verbosity of model code. In the near future, `climt` will provide an additional class called `Federation` which automates the process of creating a model from its components. `Federation` would not require that the user know the difference between a `TendencyComponent` and `Stepper` (for instance) and their different call signatures, or that `TendencyComponents` require a `TendencyStepper` to step the model state forward in time. This makes creating models easy especially for those who are not familiar with climate modelling. The tradeoff is that the run script will not explicitly describe the sequence of the main loop because that information is hidden within the `Federation` code, but this can be desirable for certain applications, particularly in education. As mentioned before, this automation is possible only because of the rich taxonomy of components `symp1` provides.

2.5.3 Features and software engineering

`climt` currently has the following components that can be used to build models⁴:

- RRTMG longwave and shortwave radiative transfer [11]: This is a Fortran component accessed via a cython wrapper. RRTMG is a state-of-the-art radiative transfer code used in many climate models.
- Grey gas radiation scheme: simulates radiative transfer in a grey gas. This component is accompanied by another component that provides an optical depth distribution which mimics the effect of water vapour [21]. These components are written in pure Python. This radiative scheme has been used in many idealised climate dynamics simulations to isolate the thermodynamic effects of latent heat release from the radiative effects of water vapour, which is a strong greenhouse gas.
- Insolation: This component is written in pure Python. It provides the solar zenith angle based on the time available in the model state. This zenith angle is used in radiative transfer codes. Currently, this component uses approximations and orbital parameters which make it highly accurate for earth but inapplicable to other planets.
- Emanuel convection scheme [17]: This is a Fortran component accessed via a Cython wrapper. It is a mass flux based convection scheme which is based on the boundary layer quasi-equilibrium hypothesis [48].
- Grid scale condensation: This is written in pure Python. It calculates the water vapour and temperature fields in the atmosphere after condensing out excess water vapour to keep the atmospheric column from becoming super-saturated.
- Spectral dynamical core: This component is derived from the General Forecast System (<https://github.com/jswhit/gfs-dycore>). It is a Fortran module accessed via a

⁴All components written in pure Python were written by the authors for use in `climt`.

cython wrapper. It uses a high performance spherical harmonics library `shtns` (<https://bitbucket.org/nschaeff/shtns>). It is parallelised using OpenMP [12], and therefore is most effective on shared memory systems. The dynamics is stepped using an implicit-explicit total variation diminishing Runge-Kutta 3 time-stepper. The physics tendencies are stepped forward using a forward Euler scheme.

- Simple Physics package for idealised simulations [50]: This is a fortran module accessed via a cython wrapper. It provides initial conditions which can be used for testing moist dynamical cores, and also provides a simple diffusive boundary layer suitable for idealised simulations.
- Slab surface: This component is written in pure Python. It allows for a prognostic surface temperature by calculating the surface energy budget. It is flexible enough to represent land or ocean. It currently does not account for localised heat fluxes.
- Sea/land ice model which allows for snow and ice layers, and energy balanced top and bottom surfaces. This component is written in pure Python. It is flexible enough to represent ice/snow growth and melting. It is capable of representing sea or land ice based on the surface type available in the model state. It currently cannot handle fractional land surface types.
- Held-Suarez forcing [27]: This component is written in pure Python. It provides an idealised set of model physics which can be used for testing dry dynamical cores and idealised simulations.
- Initial conditions from the dynamical core MIP (DCMIP) (<https://www.earthsystemcog.org/projects/dcmip/>): This is a Fortran module accessed via a cython wrapper. It provides initial conditions for a wide variety of tests which allow assessing the conservation properties of dynamical cores.

This set of components allow building a hierarchy of models ranging from single column radiative-convective models to energy balanced moist atmospheric general circulation models. Because of the fine-grained configurability of `symp1/climt`, the difference between the number of lines of code required to build a single column model and a moist GCM is only around 10 lines of Python code (see scripts in supplementary material). More importantly, most of the code is reusable when moving from a simpler to a more complex model.

Both `symp1` and `climt` are open source projects, licensed under a permissive BSD license. Both packages are available on Mac, Linux and Windows platforms, and can be directly installed from the Python Package Index using one line commands:

```
pip install symp1
pip install climt
```

eliminating the need to download source code from GitHub. The Python Package Index projects are located at <https://pypi.python.org/pypi/symp1> and <https://pypi.python.org/pypi/climt> respectively.

`climt` also provides binary releases on all supported platforms, eliminating the need to have a compiler on the user's system. `symp1` is written in pure Python, and does not have any compiler requirements. Both packages are regression tested using the online services TravisCI (<https://travis-ci.org/>) and AppVeyor (<https://www.appveyor.com/>). Both packages also maintain regularly updated documentation at <http://symp1.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> and <http://climt.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.

2.6 *Some benchmark simulations*

The first simulation is that of an atmospheric column that is run to equilibrium in the presence of radiation and convection. This model uses the RRTMG longwave and shortwave components, the Emanuel convection scheme, the Simple Physics component as its boundary layer scheme and a slab ocean of thickness 50 metres. The model timestep is 5 minutes and the results presented in Fig. 2.8 are the mean between 15000 and 20000 timesteps. The

Figure 2.8: The mean equilibrium profiles in the radiative convective single column model. The mean temperature is presented in the left panel, along with the dry and moist adiabats which are orange and green respectively. The mean heating profiles are presented in the right panel, which shows a stratosphere in radiative equilibrium and a troposphere in radiative-convective equilibrium.

air temperature transitions from a dry adiabat in the boundary layer to a moist adiabat in the free atmosphere until the tropopause. The diabatic heating balance changes from a balance between radiation and convection in the troposphere of the model to a pure radiative equilibrium in the stratosphere.

The second simulation is of a idealised aquaplanet GCM with fixed equinoctial insolation. As mentioned before, the modular nature of our framework allows re-use of much of the manuscript code from the above single column model. It consists of all the components used in the previous model along with a dynamical core which is used as the time stepper. The model was run for two years and the results presented are the mean over the last six months. The simulated climate of the model is as expected from such a configuration: the zonal mean zonal winds show two strong westerly jets which penetrate to the surface. The zonal mean temperature shows a distinct tropical cold point and an increase in the temperature

above the tropopause. The zonal mean convective heating rate shows deep heating in the tropics and much shallower heating in the subtropical areas dominated by descent of air. This simulation ran at a resolution of 128 longitudes, 62 latitudes (or T42 resolution) and 28 levels.

2.7 Conclusions and Future Avenues

`symp1` and `climt` represent a novel approach to climate modelling which provides the user with fine-grained control over the configuration of the model. `symp1` provides a rich set of entities which describe all functionality typically expected of a climate model. This set of entities (or classes) allows `climt` to be an easy to use climate modelling toolkit by allowing decisions about model creation and configuration to be made at a single location (the run script) and without ambiguity. The modular nature of the packages allows for code reuse as one traverses the hierarchy of models from single column model to three dimensional GCMs. We attempt to address concerns about plug-and-play type architectures [45] by ensuring the inputs and outputs of each model are cleanly documented, which makes it clear whether components are compatible or not. The use of Python allows for delegating computationally intensive code to compiled languages while still providing an intuitive and clean interface to the user. This choice also allows users access to a large variety of libraries written in Python for purposes ranging from machine learning to visualisation [2].

The main focus in the near future would be to add more components, especially a cloud microphysics scheme, to allow `symp1/climt` to simulate a more realistic benchmark climate. Due to its flexibility, we believe our modelling framework is well suited to the simulation of general planetary atmospheres and for exoplanet modelling, and adding components relevant to these fields will also be a priority. Another important component to add would be a flexible grid interpolation component to allow interaction between components based on different model grids. While care has been taken to ensure that parallel computing is possible, we have yet to address the question of distributed memory and computing. While building models in a simple MPI scenario seems feasible in the near future, more sophisticated configurations

Figure 2.9: The zonal mean equilibrium profiles in the idealised GCM runs with no seasonal cycle. The plotted fields are, in clockwise order from the top left, the zonal winds, air temperature, convective heating rate and specific humidity respectively. The y-axis is in model levels and x axis is in degrees.

with components running in parallel will need some thought and design.

Nevertheless, `symp1` and `climt` represent an important step towards creating flexible, usable and readable models. We hope that they will be a useful addition to the growing collection of Python based tools available to the climate science community.

Chapter 3

CLOSING HIGHER ORDERS WITH MACHINE LEARNING PARAMETERIZATION (CHOMP)

3.1 Introduction

As discussed in Chapter 1, machine learning may be an appropriate solution to improving climate model representation of subgrid processes, given the slow progression of traditional parameterizations. Here we explore one potential machine learning approach, using large-eddy simulation data as a reference dataset to train a machine learning model. The framework used for the model is that of a higher-order turbulence closure (HOC), as discussed below in Section 3.2. The goal is to improve on the current state-of-the-art HOC model, CLUBB [23], that is described in Section 3.3.

We start by introducing some concepts from machine learning and how it can be applied as a closure assumption in Section 3.4. After discussing the dataset to be used for training and testing in Section 3.5, we discuss specifics of the machine learning approaches used in Section 3.6.

We explore promising diagnostic results in predicting required parameterization outputs in Section 3.7. Using the relatively small high-resolution model dataset are unable to produce a stable prognostic model. Difficulties encountered and reasons for them are discussed in Section 3.8. These lessons were used in designing the approach for MARBLE, a more successful machine learning parameterization discussed in Chapters 4 and 5. Further thoughts on a path forward for a higher-order turbulence closure model are discussed in Chapter 6.

3.2 Higher-Order Turbulence Closure

One approach to modeling subgrid-scale turbulence in atmospheric models is Higher-Order Turbulence Closure [3] (HOC). One can decompose quantities into their mean value within a grid box and turbulent fluctuation from the mean, for example for temperature

$$T = \overline{T} + T' \quad (3.1)$$

Here an overline (\overline{T}) represents the mean and a prime (T') represents the turbulent fluctuation. From this definition, one can derive equations describing the time evolution of the grid box mean values. For example in Golaz et al. [23]:

$$\frac{\partial \overline{u}}{\partial t} = -\overline{w} \frac{\partial \overline{u}}{\partial z} - f(v_g - \overline{v}) - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \overline{u'w'}, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \overline{v}}{\partial t} = -\overline{w} \frac{\partial \overline{v}}{\partial z} + f(u_g - \overline{u}) - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \overline{v'w'}, \quad (3.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial \overline{r}_t}{\partial t} = -\overline{w} \frac{\partial \overline{r}_t}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \overline{w'r'_t} + \frac{\partial \overline{r}_t}{\partial t} \Big|_{ls}, \text{ and} \quad (3.4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \overline{\theta}_l}{\partial t} = -\overline{w} \frac{\partial \overline{\theta}_l}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \overline{w'\theta'_l} + \overline{R} + \frac{\partial \overline{\theta}_l}{\partial t} \Big|_{ls}. \quad (3.5)$$

Here \overline{R} is the radiative heating rate, f is the Coriolis parameter, u_g and v_g are the geostrophic winds in the zonal and meridional directions, r_t is total water mixing ratio, θ_l is liquid water potential temperature, and $|_{ls}$ denotes a large-scale forcing. One can derive equations again for the time evolution of the second order terms, such as [23]:

$$\frac{\partial \overline{w'r'_t}}{\partial t} = -\overline{w} \frac{\partial \overline{w'r'_t}}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial \overline{w'^2 r'_t}}{\partial z} - \frac{\overline{w'^2}}{w'^2} \frac{\partial \overline{r}_t}{\partial z} - \frac{\overline{w'r'_t}}{w'r'_t} \frac{\partial \overline{w}}{\partial z} + \frac{g}{\theta_0} \frac{\overline{r'_t \theta'_v}}{r'_t \theta'_v} - \frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\overline{r'_t \partial p'}}{\partial z} - \epsilon_{wr_t} \quad (3.6)$$

Here g is gravitational acceleration, ρ_0 is reference density, θ_0 is reference potential temperature, and ϵ denotes the molecular dissipation term.

One can continue to write equations for higher-order terms, but eventually one must make a “closure assumption”. This assumption defines prognosed tendencies from other terms that are already prognosed. This closure assumption forms the basis of a higher-order turbulence closure. For example, assuming the column is composed of two sections, such as an updraft and downdraft, having uniform conditions within each section, provides a closure assumption. Molecular dissipation ϵ and the pressure perturbation term such as $\overline{r'_t \frac{\partial p'}{\partial z}}$ must also be parameterized.

3.3 Closing moments with CLUBB

3.3.1 Assuming a Joint Double Gaussian PDF

Cloudy Layers Unified By Binormals, or CLUBB, is described in detail by Golaz et al. [23], Larson and Golaz [35]. It uses a closure assumption that the joint probability density function of total water mixing ratio q_t , liquid water potential temperature θ_l , and vertical velocity w within a grid cell follow a specific analytic form of a double Gaussian. Under this assumption, the double Gaussian is uniquely determined by second and lower order quantities. Once this probability density function is found, it can be integrated over to determine any higher-order quantities of q_t , θ_l , and w . Quantities involving pressure perturbations are closed using separate assumptions that come from earlier literature.

The joint double Gaussian form of PDF is motivated by the idea that one might expect a mode of variability corresponding to a stratiform section of the grid cell, and another mode corresponding to the convective section of the grid cell, and that each of these sections can have their variability represented by a Gaussian joint PDF.

While this motivation is appealing to model developers who have worked for decades to join parameterizations of convective and stratiform cloud layers, the literature on CLUBB shows no observational evidence supporting these two assumptions. Bogenschutz et al. [6] displays joint PDFs obtained from high-resolution models, and compares them with fits from a single and double joint Gaussian. In both cases shown, shallow cumulus and deep

Figure 3.1: Figure 4 from Bogenschutz et al. [6], showing PDF from large-eddy simulation of a shallow cumulus case. q_t is total water mixing ratio, here referred to as r_t .

convection, the joint PDF has the form of a single local and global maximum surrounded by a somewhat Gaussian form and a long tail in one direction, with some curvature in the tail. The use of a double Gaussian to represent this PDF leads to results that look very different from the target given by the models, and that have different physical meanings.

For example, the PDFs from the shallow cumulus case can be seen in Figure 3.1, with the Analytic Double Gaussian 1 (ADG1) fit of that pdf in Figure 3.2. Inspecting the joint PDF of w and q_t in Figure 3.1, we see that most of the variability comes in the form of random variations about the mean q_t with slight overall subsidence. The mean subsidence is significantly less than the variability of the vertical motions. As we focus down to parts of

Figure 3.2: Figure 5b from Bogenschutz et al. [6], showing ADG1 fit of PDF in Figure 3.1.

the grid cell where q_t exceeds 15.5 g/kg, we start to get vertical motion, with more vertical motion where we have peak moisture at around 17 g/kg. In the ADG1 fit of the PDF (Figure 3.2), the tail of the distribution is completely separated from the main variability, creating two maxima in the joint PDF where only one exists in the data being fit. This creates sets of values that never existed in the data being fit, such as $(w, q_t) = (1.5, 15)$, and destroys values that do exist in the data, such as $(w, q_t) = (0.8, 16)$. Fitch [19] looked at the same shallow cumulus case and improved the double Gaussian fit of higher-order statistics with a numerically solved PDF, but even with the best fit found "fundamental limitations, with the double-Gaussian PDF unable to represent extreme departures from Gaussian turbulence statistics, seen in the center of cumulus cloud layers examined here".

Since each Gaussian possesses no internal skewness, and the standard deviation of each Gaussian is chosen to be equal, the skewness of vertical velocity and the separation of the Gaussian centers uniquely determine the fraction of variability given to each Gaussian in the joint double PDF. The fraction corresponding to the smaller Gaussian is called a . The portion attributed to these two factors is determined by $\widetilde{\sigma}_w$, the ratio of the standard deviation of a single Gaussian to the standard deviation of the entire distribution. As this constant approaches 0, a approaches 0 and the separation gets arbitrarily large. At a value of 1, the separation approaches 0 and a again approaches 0.

The ADG1 additionally assumes no subplume correlation between w and r_t or between w and θ_t . Inspecting Figure 3.1, this is clearly an inaccurate assumption. We see correlation between these quantities throughout the variability, rather than correlation arising solely from the means of two separate Gaussians of variability. The upper right 2D panel of Figure 3.2 is somewhat puzzling, given the subplume correlation of r_t and θ_t is supposed to be equal in each plume.

Here it should be emphasized that we are only assessing the ability of the joint double Gaussian to fit data that is already known perfectly. There is the additional problem that one might not expect imperfectly fit states to correctly evolve with time.

3.3.2 CLUBB details

CLUBB closes the higher-order moment equations at second order, with the exception of $\overline{w^3}$ being prognosed at third order. As a result, prognostic equations are used for θ_l , r_t , w , $\overline{w'r'_t}$, $\overline{w'\theta'_l}$, $\overline{r'_t\theta'_l}$, $\overline{w'^2}$, $\overline{r'^2_t}$, $\overline{\theta'^2_l}$, and $\overline{w'^3}$. Diagnosed quantities include cloud fraction \overline{C} , liquid water mixing ratio $\overline{r_l}$, $\overline{r'^2_t}$, $\overline{w'r'^2_t}$, $\overline{w'^2r'_t}$, $\overline{w'\theta'^2_l}$, $\overline{w'^2\theta'_l}$, $\overline{w'r'_t\theta'_l}$, $\overline{w'r'_l}$, $\overline{r'_lr'_l}$, $\overline{\theta'_lr'_l}$, and $\overline{w'^4}$.

Additionally, the molecular dissipation terms such as ϵ_{www} and pressure perturbation terms such as $\overline{w'^2\frac{\partial p'}{\partial z}}$ are defined to partially or fully cancel out other terms such as buoyant production, and additionally damp the terms. This assumption is entirely independent from the use of a joint PDF, and yet it accounts for one of the two largest terms in the tendency budget for the moments.

The full mathematical details of CLUBB may be found in existing literature, particularly Golaz et al. [23] for the basic equations and Larson and Golaz [35] for details of the joint double Gaussian closure. The modern version of CLUBB used in models has further differences, particularly flux limiters and additional parameters, that we ignore here.

3.4 Machine Learning as a Closure Assumption

High-resolution models such as Cloud Resolving Models (CRMs) and Large Eddy Simulations (LES) are used as a benchmark against which to test new parameterizations to use in atmospheric models. These models explicitly resolve the horizontal variability that one might see in a single grid cell of a larger model, as is meant to be represented by a parameterization. As a result, one can explicitly compute at any time all moments of these horizontally resolved quantities. The resulting dataset can provide give examples of a mapping from low-order moments to higher-order moments that can be used to train a machine learning algorithm to perform the closure required in HOC.

3.4.1 Random Forests

Random forests, originally introduced by Breiman [7], are a supervised machine learning algorithm. A random forest consists of an ensemble of decision trees, each trained on a bootstrap sample of the training dataset to create variability amongst the trees. In the case of regression, the prediction of the forest is equal to the average prediction of each of its trees.

A single decision tree determines its output by a series of binary thresholds on one of the inputs, leading to a final answer after some number of "questions" have been asked of the input data point. One can compare this to the game *20 Questions*, where a player can ask a series of 20 yes or no questions to determine the secret identity of the other player. The "question" asked (in the form of checking whether an input is above or below a threshold) can depend on the series of answers given previously.

This means that the decision tree is a piecewise continuous function of its inputs. The same output value will be given as the inputs change until one of the input values crosses one of the thresholds. The forest itself, being a sum of piecewise continuous functions, is also a piecewise continuous function.

The full details of how such a model is trained can be found in Breiman [7], but an important detail is that the output values of the tree are equal to the average of a set of training data samples having similar input values, according to the thresholds. This means that for a multi-output random forest, any linear relations between the outputs present in the training dataset will be retained. In other words, any relation between outputs y_1 and y_2 of the form

$$y_1 < ay_2 + b, a \in \mathbb{R}, b \in \mathbb{R} \tag{3.7}$$

will be retained.

3.5 Dataset

Large-eddy simulations are performed of observations from the Marine ARM GPCI Investigation of Clouds (MAGIC) field campaign [62] using the System for Atmospheric Modeling (SAM) [30] according to a modification of the configuration described in McGibbon and Bretherton [37]. In our simulations, autoconversion is disabled, preventing precipitation and simplifying the water budget. The model is also supplemented with online diagnostic code to accumulate averages of higher-order turbulent moments over a time period that can be specified in the run configuration. Here we show results using 60-minute average moments. Legs 4A, 5A, 6A, 7A, 10A, 11A, 12A, 14A, 15A, 16A, 17A, and 18A are used for training, and leg 15A is used for validation.

When using shorter periods shorter than 60 minutes, a disproportionately large fraction of the model tendency is attributed to short timescale (2 timestep) oscillations in the moments. This makes it impossible to produce a model that will capture the longer timescale variability in a remotely stable fashion, due to the diagnostic training approach. This might not be as significant an issue with a multi-timestep training approach (e.g. Brenowitz and Bretherton [8], or as discussed in Chapter 4).

We found that over one-hour averages, the LES moments do not form a closed budget. This is possibly due to numerical differences when computing the budget using one-hour average moments rather than snapshots, or to the use of centered differencing on a colocated grid for vertical advection rather than the scheme used by SAM on a staggered vertical grid. Inspecting the budget for $\overline{w'\theta'_l}$ (Figure 3.6), we see large errors near the inversion and additional error throughout the boundary layer. These errors are likely due to small numerical errors in the pressure and buoyancy terms (e.g. $-\frac{1}{\rho_0}\overline{\theta'_l\frac{\partial p'}{\partial z}}$ and $\frac{g}{\theta_0}\overline{\theta'_l\theta'_v}$ for the tendency of $\overline{w'\theta'_l}$), which cannot be properly shown in the scale of the figure. For reference, the difference between these terms is shown trailing out of the figure near the inversion, and is on the order of 0.1. A slight vertical shift in either the buoyancy or pressure term as one might expect from numerical error or due to the approximation of one-hour moments is sufficient

Figure 3.3: Comparison of budget for $\overline{w'\theta'_i}$ computed from LES moments and from CHOMP polynomial fit outputs for one hour in leg 15A.

to explain the tendency error at the inversion.

To correct this, we fold the difference between the LES budget and the model tendency into the buoyancy and pressure terms, which are in turn predicted only as a sum.

3.6 Machine learning details

We use machine learning models to perform the higher-order closure independently at each vertical level. This has the advantage that the trained model can learn from relations seen at all heights. The main disadvantage is that the algorithm cannot learn any information about vertical structure or correlations that exist in the output values but not the input values. Inputs used differ slightly between the two machine learning approaches used, and are described below. Outputs include all higher-order turbulent moments predicted by CLUBB,

and additionally a representation of the pressure correlation term that is parameterized in CLUBB. Specifically, for each prognostic moment that includes a pressure correlation term, we predict the sum of the pressure and buoyancy terms, due to the large degree of cancellation occurring between these two terms. For example, for $\overline{w'\theta'_l}$ we predict $-\frac{1}{\rho_0}\overline{\theta'_l\frac{\partial p'}{\partial z}} + \frac{g}{\theta_0}\overline{\theta}_l\theta_v$. The higher-order turbulent moments and diagnostic quantities predicted include cloud fraction \overline{C} , liquid water mixing ratio \overline{r}_l , $\overline{w'r_t'^2}$, $\overline{w'^2r_t'}$, $\overline{w'\theta_t'^2}$, $\overline{w'^2\theta_t'}$, $\overline{w'r_t'\theta_t'}$, and $\overline{w'^4}$.

3.6.1 Random Forest

We use the multi-output random forest implementation included in scikit-learn [42]. 32 trees are used with a maximum depth of 16 and a minimum leaf sample count of 4. At each split, the training algorithm uses the best input feature out of 5 randomly selected features from the 12 available.

Input features include air pressure, an approximation of static stability N^2 , total water mixing ratio r_t , liquid water potential temperature θ_l , vertical wind w , and the higher-order moments $\overline{w'r_t'}$, $\overline{w'\theta_l'}$, $\overline{r_t'\theta_l'}$, $\overline{w'^2}$, $\overline{r_t'^2}$, $\overline{\theta_l'^2}$, and $\overline{w'^3}$. These include all prognostic lower-order moments used by CLUBB, with the addition of static stability defined as:

$$N^2 = \frac{g}{\theta_l} \frac{d\theta_l}{dz} \quad (3.8)$$

This differs from the true static stability in its use of θ_l in place of θ , which is done only to simplify the model.

3.6.2 Polynomial Fit

Polynomial fitting was attempted as a model that would have less noisy vertical profiles than the random forest. Vertically continuous input profiles will return vertically continuous output profiles when applying a polynomial to the input profiles. To reduce the number of terms, we use L1 regularization with an alpha coefficient of 0.1.

For the polynomial fit, we consider all first and second-order terms in the input quantities.

The inputs used include the inputs specified for the random forest, and additionally the values of C and r_l output by CLUBB. We add these as input features because the polynomial fit itself is ill-suited to predicting the vertical structure of these quantities, which does not resemble the vertical structure of any other input. All input quantities are normalized so their variance is zero in the training dataset, but are not offset by their mean.

Ideally the fit would be completed using L1 regularization over all possible first and second-order terms of the inputs, but this could not be done as the resulting dataset does not fit into memory, due to each polynomial term needing to be pre-computed before the linear regression step. Instead, we first disregard second-order terms that are unlikely to add skill to the fit. For each second-order term, we obtain an L1 regularized fit using all first-order terms and the second-order term. We only consider the second-order term if the resulting fit is at least 5% more skillful than the fit using only first-order terms. For example, if the first-order fit has a squared correlation coefficient R^2 of 0.8, the fit including the second-order term must have a skill of at least 0.84 for the second-order term to be considered.

Once the list of candidate second-order terms is compiled, we perform the polynomial fit with all first-order terms and the candidate second-order terms. The L1 regularization forces many of the coefficients to zero, and those terms are discarded. This produces a relatively sparse (fewer than 10 terms) polynomial representation of the outputs. The L1 regularization coefficient was optimized to produce higher performance on the validation dataset (the best generalizable model), but also to produce a simpler model that is easier to diagnose in a prognostic setting.

Furthermore, the polynomial fit is done in two stages, where a second stage is used for computing the sum of the buoyancy and pressure terms for the prognostic variables $\overline{w'^2}$, $\overline{w'^3}$, $\overline{w'\theta_l}$, and $\overline{w'r'_l}$. The initial stage predicts all other outputs listed in Section 3.6, and additionally the liquid water correlation terms $\overline{w'r'_l}$, $\overline{w'^2r'_l}$, $\overline{\theta'_l r'_l}$, and $\overline{r'_l r'_l}$. These liquid water correlation terms allow us to compute the buoyancy terms, which are determined in large part directly from prognostic moments.

In the second stage, we make changes to the set of inputs used. The inputs $\overline{r_t}$, $\overline{\theta_l}$, and

\bar{w} are excluded. The buoyancy terms of $\overline{w'^2}$, $\overline{w'^3}$, $\overline{w'\theta_l}$, and $\overline{w'r'_t}$ are computed directly from prognostic variables and outputs of the first stage and included as inputs. The vertical derivatives of $\overline{w'^3}$ and $\overline{w'^4}$ (the latter predicted by the first stage) are also included as inputs. This is akin to including the turbulent advection terms for $\overline{w'^2}$ and $\overline{w'^3}$ as inputs.

3.7 Evaluating CLUBB diagnostically against machine learning

We will evaluate the machine learning closures and CLUBB on leg 15A of MAGIC, which was withheld for validation.

First we inspect some example vertical profiles of predicted higher-order moments. Figure 3.4 shows profiles from the initial cumulus regime following stratocumulus break-up. We see for several quantities, such as $\overline{w'r_t'^2}$ and $\overline{w'^2\theta'_l}$, that the random forest does a better job of producing some smaller-scale features than the polynomial fit. This suggests there are additional nonlinear structures that can be learned from the training data that are not captured by the polynomial fit. We also see that the profiles produced by the random forest are relatively noisy in the vertical. This is due to the piecewise continuous relationship between the inputs and outputs of the random forest. It can be alleviated somewhat by increasing the number of trees used, but only to a limited extent. The performance of these schemes in the cumulus regime shown is generally reflective of the performance throughout the simulation, apart from within an approximately 10 hour segment of stratocumulus regime we discuss below.

We also see large errors in the representation of the higher-order terms by CLUBB. Inversion peaks of $\overline{w'r_t'^2}$ and $\overline{w'\theta_l'^2}$ are significantly over-estimated, while the peaks for $\overline{w'^2r_t'}$ and $\overline{w'^2\theta'_l}$ are missing entirely (we see only the bump from below the inversion). CLUBB does a reasonable job of predicting the vertical structures of C , r_l , and $\overline{w'^4}$, but not the magnitudes.

From hours 29 to 39, the machine learning fits show significant bias within the boundary layer. Figure 3.5 shows a representative profile. Given the high performance on the rest of the simulation, one would expect this is due to the variability present being outside the

Figure 3.4: Profiles from hour 55 of leg 15A in cumulus regime.

range of variability in the training runs.

Inspecting the performance statistics of the machine learning closures and CLUBB, we see results reflective of what we see in the individual profiles (which makes sense, given the statistics are only for one 4.5-day simulation). CLUBB performs well on \bar{C} , \bar{r}_l , and $\overline{w^4}$, but is significantly outperformed on the other moments. This is possibly due to the tuning process in CLUBB and to the importance of each term for prognostic performance. In Bogenschutz et al. [6], emphasis is placed on \bar{C} , \bar{r}_l , and $\overline{w^4}$.

The performance in predicting the sum of the buoyancy and pressure terms for $\overline{w^2}$ is exceedingly high, at over 99.9% of variance explained. This is noteworthy because of the simplicity of the representation. The fit is only one linear term that partially cancels turbulent advection. A similar one-term fit is also used for the sum of the buoyancy and pressure terms for $\overline{w^3}$. This is due to the cancellation between turbulent advection and buoyant production at the inversion dominating the variability in this term over the MAGIC dataset. It would be of interest to investigate whether this balance dominates under entirely different

Figure 3.5: Profiles from hour 35 of leg 15A in stratocumulus regime.

Figure 3.6: Bias and squared correlation coefficient for CLUBB, random forest, and polynomial fit over Leg 15A. Evaluation is performed on values normalized such that their mean is zero and variance is 1 over the MAGIC training legs. Equal weighting is given to each model level. $|_{b,p}$ denotes the sum of the tendency from the buoyancy and pressure terms, as described in Section 3.5.

regimes without strong inversion layers, due to the appealing simplicity of this representation.

One might expect the lower predictive power for the buoyancy terms of $\overline{w'\theta'_l}$ and $\overline{w'r'_t}$ is due to having not included the turbulent advective terms of these quantities as possible inputs, as described in Section 3.6.2. However, including these as inputs reduced error on the training dataset by only roughly 10% of the error amount, and lowered performance slightly on the validation dataset.

3.8 Challenges for Prognostic Integration

Despite good diagnostic performance of the random forest closure, we were unable to translate this into a prognostically integrable model primarily due to the noise in the vertical profiles it produces. The prognostic equations for the lower-order moments generally rely on vertical derivatives of the higher-order moments, rather than the moments themselves. The profiles produced by the random forest have excessively noisy vertical derivatives. Another way of framing this issue for both schemes is that the prognostic moment equations generally depend on the vertical derivative of the higher-order moments, whereas we have optimized only for the value of the higher-order moments.

We can see the impact of this error in Figure 3.7. The prognostic variable $\overline{w'\theta'_l}$ has a tendency term proportional to the vertical derivative of $\overline{w'^2\theta'_l}$. At the first timestep, we see the sharp gradients in the higher-order moment produce spikes in the prognostic variable. The noisy prognostic moments in turn produce more noise in the higher-order moments that are diagnosed from the prognostic moments, creating a feedback loop. Within 5 timesteps, this has produced a large amount of noise in the prognostic moment.

In the case of the polynomial closure, the equations that result from inserting polynomial fits for the higher-order moments can easily produce problematic behaviors. For example, Figure 3.8 shows the growth of the first instability we encountered. Following what is shown in this figure, $\overline{\theta}_l$ develops negative values causing the model to crash.

We did not diagnose the exact cause of the instability in Figure 3.8, but instead found that we could remove it by sufficiently damping $\overline{w'^3}$. Unfortunately, the instability appeared

Figure 3.7: Snapshots of the vertical profiles of $\overline{w'\theta'_i}$ and $\overline{w'^2\theta'_i}$ at three timesteps of a prognostic run using the random forest closure, using a timestep of 0.5 seconds.

Figure 3.8: Timeseries showing growth of instability in CHOMP. "turb adv" refers to turbulent advection term, and "buoyancy" refers to the sum of the buoyancy and pressure terms. Length of integration is approximately 15 minutes.

in the boundary layer later in the simulation, and could not be damped sufficiently without gross deterioration of model performance in the boundary layer. We continued to diagnose the model while freezing $\overline{w'^3}$, but continued to find issues. Within the prognostic equations, we can easily get systems of the form:

$$\frac{d\overline{w'\theta'_l}}{dt} = c \frac{d\overline{w'\theta'_l}}{dz}, c \in \mathbb{R} \quad (3.9)$$

that produce a vertical drift of the existing profile that we had observed in $\overline{w'^3}$, or systems like

$$\frac{d\overline{w'\theta'_l}}{dt} = c_1 \overline{w'r'_t}, c_1 \in \mathbb{R} \quad (3.10)$$

$$\frac{d\overline{w'r'_t}}{dt} = c_2 \overline{w'\theta'_l}, c_2 \in \mathbb{R} \quad (3.11)$$

that can produce either growth, decay, or oscillations depending on the signs of c_1 , c_2 , $\overline{w'r'_t}$, and $\overline{w'\theta'_l}$. An example of this behavior is shown in Figure 3.9, where $\overline{w'^3}$ is fixed. This is not limited to linear terms; second-order terms can produce similar behaviors, for example when one of the factors in the term is relatively constant or at least maintains its sign.

Given the polynomial closure does a great job at diagnostically predicting the higher-order moments, why do we see such poor prognostic performance? An important issue when training any kind of machine learning higher-order turbulence closure is that the tendency of the second-order moments is about two orders of magnitude smaller than the terms that form the tendency. As a result, small errors in individual terms can lead to large errors in the tendency. This point is underscored by the fact that even the budget computed using higher-order moments obtained directly from the LES is not closed because of numerical differences.

A better approach may be to focus on predicting second-order moment tendencies directly, but this has its own set of difficulties. This would prove challenging to do with polynomial fitting, as we still have the issue of the resulting equations producing runaway and oscillatory

Figure 3.9: 2000 second integration of CHOMP with fixed $\overline{w'^3}$ and a constant turbulent length scale of 5 km.

feedbacks between terms. In the case of random forest regression, the problem of noisy vertical profiles remains. An ideal solution may be to train a neural network in the style of Brenowitz and Bretherton [8], as used in Chapter 4. This would have the additional benefit of explicitly training a model to be numerically stable and free of the problematic behaviors discussed earlier in reference to the polynomial closure. We were unable to acquire a training dataset sufficiently large to train neural networks to perform this closure diagnostically, but this may be possible with a significantly larger training dataset.

Further thoughts on how CHOMP may be made into a workable model are described in Chapter 6.

3.9 Using Python for model development

In writing the prognostic version of CHOMP, the Sympl framework described in Chapter 2 was used. This had the benefit of allowing us to use the Python implementation of the parameterization directly, which was useful given the model was trained in Python. This prevented needing to re-write the model in a compiled language such as Fortran.

Overall, using Python as the core language to develop CHOMP greatly accelerated investigation and simplified the development process. It made it trivial to incorporate online analysis code into the model, experiment with adding components like limiters or change parameters, freeze prognostic variables that were known to have issues when integrated, and immediately see plots of the resulting simulations. We would strongly recommend developing a new parameterization in an interactive language like Python that is well-suited to this type of prototyping.

There is a question, however, of whether it makes sense to develop using Sympl or whether it is sufficient to write one's own model in its entirety. The main of using this framework is that one immediately has access to a certain set of components to use in a model. Particularly you have access to time steppers, simple plotting objects, and the parameterizations from CliMT. A secondary benefit is that by using Sympl, you adopt the set of coding best practices that Sympl is designed to make you use. Specifically, you must fully document the

components you write, and those components must be modular and self-contained.

What we found was the main drawback in using Sympl was the strong enforcement of using long names to refer to variables, with a lack of support for using shorter aliases within the main model script. This could be rectified by adding to Sympl a new type of `dict` object that uses registered aliases to allow you to use shorter names to refer to variables. This would require initially writing out in code the mapping from shorter aliases to longer names, but that would have to be done only once instead of many times in the course of writing and re-writing code within the main model script. One could write one's own Python object to do this if so inclined, or even submit the code for inclusion in Sympl.

It also can require significant boilerplate code to convert all of one's arrays into `DataArray` objects with specified dimensions and units. Some of the boilerplate is unavoidable. For example, it is unavoidable to specify explicitly the dimensions and units of each quantity you are using, if that information is to be made available to Sympl. The hope is that this saves work in the long run for the model developer who goes back and reads their own code, or shares it with others. However, this boilerplate code could be simplified by new helper functions that perform some of the work for the model developer.

3.10 Why does CLUBB work?

Given a scheme that more accurately produces higher-order moments fails to produce meaningful results when run prognostically, one might ask how it is that CLUBB does any better. Unlike the machine learning closure, CLUBB is a system of equations with negative feedbacks that ensure a balance of terms is achieved. The equations are formulated so that pressure perturbation correlations explicitly cancel out large fractions or the entirety of other terms. This term is one of the two largest terms in the tendency budgets, and CLUBB uses a highly simplified representation for this term that is designed to produce a stable model rather than to fit a set of observed moments. CHOMP on the other hand fails to be stable because it attempts to fit the moments well while disregarding stability. The dissipation term in CLUBB provides an explicit negative feedback for the production of higher-order moments,

Figure 3.10: CLUBB length scale during shallow cumulus simulation [18] performed in WRF, compared to length scale derived from a Python wrapper placed over the Fortran distribution of CLUBB. Vertical axis and color bar are in units of meters. Timeseries duration is slightly more than 2 days.

and is tuned such that when combined prognostically with the mechanisms that produce those moments, a reasonable equilibrium is achieved.

As a result, CLUBB is incredibly sensitive to its choice of length scale formulation that determines the strength of the molecular dissipation damping. This length scale formulation in turn is not very well-constrained by physical motivation. We found in performing a shallow cumulus simulation as described in Endo et al. [18] that the length scale sporadically behaved as though deep convection were present when in fact there was none (Figure 3.10).

On the whole CLUBB is formulated in a way that encourages stability, makes heavy use of limiters and dissipation, and has sufficient knobs to fit the desired behavior competitively well or better than its competitors for the cases we have available for testing.

Ideally a model should be constructed from first principles on a solid physical basis and we would like to see that physical basis lead to reasonable results when the model is run. This grants confidence that the model will perform well outside of the range of its training data (our observational record). Insofar as CLUBB does not conform to a solid physical basis, it is difficult to be confident in its results past what we are able to use to train (or

”develop” in this case) the model (including high-resolution simulations of future climate). Its results should be scrutinized and validated just as strongly as a machine learning model.

Chapter 4

MACHINE ASSISTED REANALYSIS BOUNDARY LAYER EMULATION (MARBLE)

4.1 Introduction

In Chapter 3, we found significant difficulties in using LES to train a machine-learning closure for higher-order turbulent moments in CLUBB that can be used with a prognostic atmospheric dynamics model. This was owing mainly to the small dataset size and also to CLUBB’s complexity. In this chapter, we take a completely different and more successful approach to using machine learning to design a parameterization for cloud-topped boundary layers. We shift to the use of a reanalysis dataset, and predict the tendencies of mean thermodynamic quantities rather than higher-order moments.

Using reanalysis allows our model to learn not only from the conventional parameterization used in the global forecast model, but also from the observational update or ‘analysis increment’ applied in the data assimilation cycle. This update provides a natural bias correction to the conventional model, which can improve performance compared to the parameterization suite of the forecast model used to create the reanalysis. In this study, we focus on the summertime Northeast Pacific, a particularly well-studied subtropical transition region (e.g. Stevens et al. [53], Zhou et al. [61], Albrecht et al. [1]) with large horizontal gradients of sea-surface temperature (SST) and climatological low cloud cover. To speed up training, we limit the domain size and the scope of the network to be able to sufficiently sample the variability with a dataset that fits in the 4GB of memory available on our GPU. However, there is no fundamental reason the same approach could not be applied globally using computational resources sufficient to process the larger volume of data, for example by using multiple GPUs training in parallel.

We use an artificial neural network (ANN) to predict the lower-tropospheric heating and moistening tendencies in each model grid column. An ANN is a nonlinear machine learning model trained by iteratively modifying a large number of model weights to optimize a loss function. ANNs have been used successfully to emulate radiation in a prognostic setting [33] and to diagnose cloud fraction and precipitation [34]. More recently they have been used to represent convection in a prognostic setting, using deep networks on superparameterization model data [47] and a novel approach to prognostic model training on near-global cloud-resolving model data [8].

We begin by discussing the reanalysis dataset (Section 4.2) and outline the MARBLE model (Section 4.3). This is followed by an evaluation of MARBLE’s performance over the Northeast Pacific (Section 4.4). Finally, we summarize key strengths of MARBLE and discuss future extensions of this data-driven machine-learning parameterization approach (Section 4.5).

4.2 Dataset

The European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) Reanalysis 5th Generation (ERA5) is a global reanalysis dataset, documented at:

<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CKB/ERA5+data+documentation>

In this study we use the high-resolution realization (HRES) run at 31km horizontal resolution, which provides hourly data on 31 model levels in the vertical domain we are modeling (from the surface to 3km). Our study uses reanalysis data for June-August 2008-2016 over the Northeast Pacific on a 0.5° grid from 230°W - 215°W and 25°N - 40°N , as shown in Figure 4.1.

MARBLE is trained and evaluated on hourly values in June, July, and August. For state quantities such as temperature, surface pressure, vertical wind, humidity, or mixing ratios, instantaneous values are used. For flux quantities such as surface precipitation or radiative fluxes, hourly mean values are used. Data from 2008 through 2014 are used for training, and validation is performed on 2015 data to determine a reasonable model configuration.

Figure 4.1: Study region used for model training and evaluation. The blue square indicates the region of study.

Data from 2016 are used for evaluation once all model configuration has been determined, including number of neurons, depth of network, choice of activation function, etc.

4.3 Model Description

Following most conventional climate model parameterizations, we use a vertically nonlocal column-oriented approach. The diabatic heating and moistening tendencies at each height within a grid column are functions of conditions throughout that grid column, but not other grid columns. Other boundary conditions at the surface or top of our simulated tropospheric layer, e. g. surface fluxes of sensible and latent heat, are allowed to affect the entire vertical column in a single time step, reflecting possible rapid vertical transport in turbulent eddies.

We apply the multi-timestep training approach used by Brenowitz and Bretherton [8] to vertically-resolved reanalysis data over the Northeast Pacific. This training approach generates a numerically stable and accurate model, whereas a model trained on tendencies

at each timestep is numerically unstable. We call this approach Machine-Assisted Reanalysis Boundary Layer Emulation (MARBLE). MARBLE replaces all subgrid and radiative heating parameterizations and resolved vertical advection within its domain. For simplicity, our implementation does not yet predict momentum tendencies.

4.3.1 Dimensionality Reduction

Rather than use the full resolution vertical profile of the ERA5 product, we reduce the dimensionality of the data using principal components on a constant height grid. Like the choice of a limited horizontal region, this is done to reduce the memory footprint of the training dataset. First, the ERA5 profiles are interpolated to an evenly spaced height grid of 20 points from the lowest model level to a height of 3km. The mean vertical profiles based on the training data (Figure 4.2) are removed. The time-height perturbations of each variable are separately decomposed into principal components. We keep enough components to explain 99% of the variability of the training data – 10 components for liquid water static energy (s_l) and total water mixing ratio (r_t) and 5 for vertical wind (Figure 4.3).

Tendencies are decomposed using the principal components of their respective prognostic variable (for example, clear-sky radiative heating rates are decomposed using the basis for s_l). All vertically-resolved quantities are input and output as principal components. All inputs and outputs are additionally normalized so that their values in the training dataset have a mean of 0 and variance of 1. After training, computed outputs are re-scaled and transformed back to a constant height grid for plotting and error evaluation.

4.3.2 Neural Network Design

The core of MARBLE is a feed-forward neural network for supervised learning. The loss functions being iteratively minimized during training are weighted sums of mean squared errors of the model outputs, as described below. They do not include any regularization terms, as L1 and L2 regularization were found not to significantly affect model generalization.

Figure 4.2: Mean vertical profiles of quantities removed before computing principal components.

Figure 4.3: Principal components and cumulative fraction of explained variance for the northeast Pacific. White corresponds to zero.

Figure 4.4: Artificial neural network structure and training approach, showing a) how components are connected in the first timestep, b) the internal structure of the ANN component, and c) how those components are chained together to train over multiple timesteps. Orange represents operations with trainable weights, grey represents static operations without trainable weights, purple represents output vectors whose values are included in the optimized loss function, green represents internal vectors used by the model, and blue represents data collected from ERA5 used as input to the model. At each timestep in c) the ANN uses the same weights. Network tendencies include both clear-sky radiative heating and residual tendencies.

MARBLE is trained while integrating forward 7 days with a one-hour forward Euler timestep, as shown in Figure 4.4. Training with a significantly shorter period of 2 days was found to produce a model that is numerically unstable within a few days, whereas after training over periods of 7 days we did not observe instability in the model even after a month-long forecast. Figure 4.4b shows the internal structure of the neural network, which has three layers and uses the rectifier linear activation function (ReLU), defined as

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

The input, internal, and output layers contain 33, 128, and 51 neurons, respectively. Figure 4.4a shows in detail how the neural network is used to compute the next model state in the course of training. The components are color coded to show their role in model training. Input forcings from the ERA5 dataset include surface latent and sensible heat flux, sea surface temperature, surface pressure, mid and high cloud fractions, downwelling shortwave fluxes at top-of-atmosphere and top-of-domain, top-of-domain rainwater mixing ratio, and the vertical structure of vertical wind decomposed into its principal components. The input to the network also includes the principal components of s_l and r_t output from the previous timestep, which on the first timestep are taken from the ERA5 dataset. These inputs include all relevant top and bottom-of-domain forcings.

The neural network produces a set of diagnostic outputs, a clear-sky radiative heating rate that is optimized to match its ERA5 counterpart, and unconstrained "residual" tendencies for s_l and r_t . This includes effects of surface fluxes, analysis increments, cloud radiative effects, and turbulence. At the inversion, there is usually substantial compensation between vertical advection (which is imperfectly represented by the reduced-dimension basis used by MARBLE) and entrainment contributions to the residual tendency. Hence, we also fold vertical advection into the residual tendency.

These tendencies, together with clear-sky radiative heating and ERA5-derived horizontal advection of heat and moisture by the mean wind, are then added to the previous model

state, producing a state at the next time step. The residual tendencies are not optimized to directly match any value in the ERA5 dataset. However, the model *is* optimized to produce thermodynamic states that match the states in ERA5, and the only way it can do this is by learning the correct form of tendency to add to the model state.

Figure 4.4c shows the full structure of the system being optimized. While not pictured, a total of 168 time units are used to step the model state forward a total of 7 days in 1-hour increments. In training, the system is considered as a single neural network whose optimized output includes diagnostic values and model state at every timestep (indicated by purple boxes).

The full equations for the tendencies at each timestep can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{ds_l}{dt} &= \frac{ds_l}{dt}_{hadv} + \mathbf{W}_{sl} \cdot ReL(\mathbf{W}_2 \cdot ReL(\mathbf{W}_3 \cdot \vec{x}_{in} + \vec{b}_3) + \vec{b}_2) + \vec{b}_{sl} \\ \frac{dr_t}{dt} &= \frac{dr_t}{dt}_{hadv} + \mathbf{W}_{rt} \cdot ReL(\mathbf{W}_2 \cdot ReL(\mathbf{W}_3 \cdot \vec{x}_{in} + \vec{b}_3) + \vec{b}_2) + \vec{b}_{rt}\end{aligned}\quad (4.2)$$

where the subscript 'hadv' denotes a prescribed horizontal advective tendency, \vec{x}_{in} is a vector containing the normalized inputs, \mathbf{W} represents trained weight matrices, and \vec{b} represents trained bias vectors. *ReL* is the rectified linear activation function as defined in Equation 4.1.

\vec{x}_{in} includes all inputs to the neural network as previously described in this section, concatenated into one vector. Horizontal advective fluxes are intentionally not included in \vec{x}_{in} to avoid the model learning the inversion height from the vertical structure of the ERA5 advective forcings, an approach that might go wrong in a three-dimensional simulation.

Using normalized outputs, the loss function being minimized is

$$\begin{aligned}E &= \frac{1}{N_s N_t} \sum_{sample} \sum_{timestep} \left(\frac{1}{z_t} \int_{z=0}^{z=z_t} \left(\frac{1}{4} [(s_l^m - s_l^a)^2 + r_t^m - r_t^a]^2 \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{1}{14} [(r_c^m - r_c^a)^2 + (r_r^m - r_r^a)^2 + (C^m - C^a)^2 + (R_{cs}^m - R_{cs}^a)^2] \right) dz \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{14} [(C_{lo}^m - C_{lo}^a)^2 + (P_s^m - P_s^a)^2 + (\mathcal{L}^m - \mathcal{L}^a)^2] \right)\end{aligned}\quad (4.3)$$

where subscript m and a refer to model and actual values respectively, N_t is number of timesteps, N_s is the number of training samples, and z_t is the height of the model domain. The remaining terms represent model outputs, as listed in the following section in Table 4.1. The weighting in the loss function is defined such that half of the weight is evenly distributed between the two prognostic terms, and the other half between diagnostic outputs.

Within MARBLE, r_t and s_l are prognostic. All other outputs are purely diagnostic and are determined directly from r_t , s_l , and model inputs. Because these diagnostic outputs are trained over the course of many timesteps in MARBLE, they can be accurately diagnosed from the kind of model state that MARBLE produces. In contrast, were we to train a diagnostic model using only ERA5 data as input, the model might perform poorly if MARBLE drifts away from ERA5-like states. We found that training a neural network to diagnose clear-sky radiative heating directly on ERA5 often produced unphysically high radiative heating rates when run prognostically in MARBLE, even at night.

Training was done using the AMSGrad variant [49] of the Adam optimizer [31] implementation in Keras, with a learning rate of 0.002 and training batches of 4096 7-day single-column samples, initialized every 5 days. The ANN was trained for 500 epochs.

4.4 Evaluation

To evaluate the model, we integrate the state forward 7 days in a single-column mode using the specified ERA5 forcings for each given testing location, initialized every 5 days. We compare with the corresponding ERA5 state and a baseline forecast, both projected onto the same reduced basis.

4.4.1 Baseline Model

The fidelity of the ERA5 reanalysis relies heavily on the skill of the underlying ECMWF forecast model. Thus, a suitable single-column-like configuration of that forecast model provides a baseline for assessing whether any skill is added by MARBLE.

To this end, we used the first 12 hours of the short-term ECMWF forecasts available as

part of ERA5. To make a 7 day 'baseline' forecast in any grid column, we accumulate the tendencies of s_t and r_t from 14 successive 12-hour forecasts, but not the differences between each 12 hour forecast and the initialization of the next forecast (which we interpret as approximating the analysis increments). This baseline is not useful for clouds and precipitation, which MARBLE treats as diagnostic variables.

Each time step we also re-project onto the 20-point evenly spaced vertical grid and perform physical adjustments, setting negative values of r_t to zero and mixing any superadiabatic lapse rates to the dry adiabat, before projecting back into principal components. When performing dry adiabatic adjustment we neglect differences in layer mass for simplicity. This process of projection and adjustment increases baseline model squared correlation coefficients (R^2) of s_t and r_t against vertical profiles from the testing data by about 4% in the latter half of 7-day simulations.

Since the advective forcings from the short-range forecasts are almost identical to those in the ERA5 analysis, this baseline provides an analogue to the ECMWF model performance in single-column mode forced similarly to MARBLE. The most obvious way MARBLE can improve on the skill of this baseline is by learning the analysis increments.

4.4.2 Results

It is illuminating to inspect one such single column model run. We selected a simulation from the testing data at random for this purpose (Figure 4.5).

MARBLE does a remarkably good job of reproducing the evolution of ERA5 boundary structure and cloud properties in this 7-day period. In contrast to the baseline simulation, there is remarkably little apparent degradation of the forecast with time. We attribute this to the strong control of the boundary-layer depth and evolution by the vertical motion and horizontal advective forcings, a form of 'slow-manifold' behavior [9]. Directly comparing the residual tendency produced by the ANN with its ERA5 counterpart, we see that MARBLE not only does very well at the inversion where tendencies are strongest, but also reproduces features in the tendency profile within the boundary layer and free troposphere. Inter-forecast

Figure 4.5: Randomly selected seven-day single-column prognostic simulation timeseries forced using withheld testing data, with comparison to ERA5 and baseline model. Initialized at 7:00 UTC on June 11, 2016 at 30°N, 133.5°W. Residual s_t and r_t tendencies have been modified by subtracting vertical advective tendencies diagnosed by centered differencing, leaving only the diabatic contributions.

Figure 4.6: Fraction of variance explained (R^2) for key quantities as a function of simulation time, averaged for each timestep across all 7-day simulations for the 2016 Northeast Pacific. Note the y-axis begins at 0.5 for clarity.

tendencies produced every 12 hours in the analysis dataset are smoothed over longer periods in MARBLE. The clear-sky radiative heating profiles closely match the diurnal cycle of radiative heating and the impact of vertical thermodynamic structure on radiative heating rates seen in the ERA5 heating profiles.

Some values can be unphysically negative, such as cloud fraction and mixing ratios. This is due in part to the use of principal components, where the projection of the real profiles onto their components can give negative values even in the training data. For the diagnostic outputs, this can be rectified by limiting the values. For total water mixing ratio, limiting may have unforeseen negative effects since it is not active during model training.

Having seen an example timeseries, we statistically evaluate MARBLE’s overall performance averaged over all NE Pacific locations and initialization times in the testing dataset. For this evaluation we use the second half of these simulations (Days 3.5-7) to avoid inheriting skill from the initial state. When we inspect model skill as a function of simulation timestep, we see the skill for s_l and r_t deteriorates gradually and levels off by 3.5 days (Figure 4.6).

MARBLE does very well at representing the thermodynamic structure and cloud prop-

Table 4.1: MARBLE performance for 2016 Northeast Pacific. Simulations described in Section 4.4. Evaluation is performed over the last 3.5 days of each 7-day simulation. The training mean at each height is subtracted before calculating the squared correlation coefficient R^2 . Baseline values are computed from the baseline model described in Section 4.4.1. Liquid water static energy is normalized by the heat capacity of dry air at constant pressure.

Quantity	Mean Bias	RMSE	R^2	Baseline R^2
liquid water static energy (s_l/C_{pd})	-0.05 K	2.8 K	0.90	0.73
total water mixing ratio (r_t)	0.065 g/kg	0.9 g/kg	0.90	0.74
clear-sky radiative heating rate (R_{cs})	0.01 K/hr	0.04 K/hr	0.73	N/A
vertically-resolved cloud fraction (C)	-0.0030	0.12	0.69	N/A
cloud water mixing ratio (r_c)	-1.3e-3 g/kg	3.4e-2 g/kg	0.65	N/A
rain water mixing ratio (r_{rain})	7.0e-5 g/kg	2.4e-3 g/kg	0.96	N/A
column low cloud fraction (C_{low})	-0.033	0.18	0.77	N/A
surface precipitation (P_s)	9.8e-3 mm/h	8.5e-2 mm/h	0.86	N/A
column cloud water (\mathcal{L})	-0.0046 kg/m ²	0.026 kg/m ²	0.85	N/A

erties of ERA5 over this region during the second half of the 7-day single-column forecasts, outperforming the baseline by a considerable margin. Despite its reduced vertical resolution, MARBLE has learned to improve upon the parameterized heating and moistening tendencies of the baseline ECMWF forecast model. The bias, root mean squared error, and fraction of explained variance for several quantities are listed in Table 1. As was seen in Figure 4.5, the largest errors are seen in vertically-resolved cloud fraction, which still shows good performance.

The horizontally-resolved mean 'climate' for JJA 2016 is shown in Figure 4.7. Despite not receiving any information about the spatial location of each sample other than sea surface temperature, MARBLE skillfully represents ERA5's stratocumulus to cumulus transition.

Figure 4.7: Horizontally-resolved mean values and correlation coefficients of key quantities, averaged across the last 3.5 days of 7-day simulations for the 2016 Northeast Pacific.

There do exist small wave-like artifacts in the machine learning output, which would likely be smoothed if the columns could communicate in the horizontal. The third column in Figure 4.7 shows that the model does a good job of reproducing the variability of ERA5 throughout the domain.

MARBLE also reproduces ERA5’s mean diurnal variability of low cloud fraction and precipitation across the NE Pacific (Figure 4.8). It produces both a thickening of low cloud and increase in precipitation during the night, with thinner cloud and lower precipitation during the day when cloud-top shortwave heating reduces turbulent mixing from cloud-top longwave cooling in this region.

4.5 Conclusions

We have shown that an ANN trained over many timesteps as in Brenowitz and Bretherton [8] does a remarkably good job of matching the thermodynamic evolution and boundary layer properties of the ERA5 reanalysis dataset over the summertime Northeast Pacific in

Figure 4.8: Mean diurnal cycle of cloud fraction and precipitation, averaged across the last 3.5 days of 7-day simulations for the 2016 Northeast Pacific in June, July, and August. Local hour is based on mean longitude.

a single column model. We have created a machine learning model, MARBLE, that learns not only to reproduce the effects of the physical parameterizations in the underlying weather forecast model, but also to add the systematic impacts of analysis increments from data assimilation on the reanalysis. This serves as a natural form of model bias correction. In this study, MARBLE was trained and applied to a particular region and season. We have also successfully trained a version of MARBLE for summertime boundary layer parameterization over the southern U. S. Great Plains, and it is being tested as the lower tropospheric diabatic process parameterization for regional boundary-forced three-dimensional simulations with a mesoscale model. If this proves successful, we will try to generalize MARBLE to work globally.

Chapter 5

MARBLE OVER THE SOUTHERN GREAT PLAINS (SGP)

5.1 *Introduction*

In Chapter 4 we introduced MARBLE and showed results of running the model in single-column mode over the Northeast Pacific. In this chapter, we show similar results over the Southern Great Plains (SGP) region.

The SGP shows important differences in its boundary layer evolution compared to the NEP, owing to differences between the land and ocean surface. Due to the much lower heat capacity of land, the diurnal cycle is much stronger, and the atmospheric thermodynamic profile shows much stronger variability. The majority of the surface heat flux is in the form of sensible heat, as opposed to latent heat flux dominating over ocean. Heterogeneity of the land surface leads to more horizontally heterogeneous atmospheric conditions, and as a result stronger horizontal advective forcings. The stable layer capping the boundary layer over the SGP is much wider than the inversion seen over the NEP, and thus more easily resolved by weather and climate models.

While the NEP is dominated by shallow convection and relatively stationary stratiform cloud layers, deep convection occurs often over the SGP. The separation between the boundary layer and the overlying free troposphere is less clear, and it is possible for precipitation to enter from the top boundary of our lower tropospheric domain. Deep convective systems may develop and advect into a given column, rather than originate from thermodynamic conditions in that column. The onset or decay of deep convection may occur over very few of our one-hour timesteps, especially when we consider horizontal advection into and out of the single column.

Figure 5.1: Study region used for model training and evaluation. The blue square indicates the region of study for the Northeast Pacific. The orange square indicates the region of study used in this chapter for the Southern Great Plains (SGP).

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5.2 Dataset

The dataset used in this chapter is identical to the one described in Chapter 4, but over the region from 265°W-260°W and 34°N-39°N, as shown in Figure 5.1. Instead of using an equally spaced vertical grid from the surface to 3km, we instead expand the grid to reach 4km to contain the occasionally deeper boundary layers found over the region. Because of the smaller domain size compared to the Northeast Pacific, we are able to include a larger temporal period in our training data. Here we additionally include April and May for a total of 5 months of data each year.

As in Chapter 4, we decompose vertically-resolved quantities into principal components after removing the vertical mean profiles (Figure 5.2). Principal components are re-computed using the training dataset over this region (Figure 5.3). In contrast to the principal compo-

Figure 5.2: Mean vertical profiles of quantities removed before computing principal components over the SGP.

ponents for the NEP, we see greater variability close to the surface, owing to the much stronger fluctuations in surface temperature over the SGP.

5.3 Network Design

The artificial neural network used is identical to the one presented in Chapter 4. The only difference is in the number of input and output neurons, due to the different number of principal components required to represent the two datasets. The neural network here includes 29 input neurons and 49 output neurons, and still uses 128 neurons in each internal layer. The training approach used is also identical with the same hyperparameters.

5.4 Evaluation

We first inspect a prognostic simulation directly to qualitatively evaluate model performance (Figure 5.4). As before, all vertically-resolved data is projected into principal components

Figure 5.3: Principal components and cumulative fraction of explained variance for the SGP. White corresponds to zero.

and then back onto the vertical dimension. This is particularly apparent in the clear-sky radiative heating profiles.

From this timeseries, we see MARBLE does a good job representing diurnal variations and tropospheric variability. As over the Northeast Pacific, vertically-resolved cloud fraction is greatly smoothed, but the model does a good job of identifying where and when clouds and convection occur. This is also reflected in the surface precipitation timeseries. The model appears to miss more fine-scale features than it did over the Northeast Pacific, such as the structure of the collapsing boundary layer around day 3 and the variability in the free troposphere at day 6. However, overall it looks qualitatively similar to the ERA5 timeseries.

We see the baseline model also does well at representing diurnal variability and many fine-scale features in this timeseries, as expected due to its construction. Within this timeseries the baseline model develops biases as the simulation progresses, including a cool and moist bias towards the top of the boundary layer and in the free troposphere. While there is some

Figure 5.4: Randomly selected seven-day single-column prognostic simulation timeseries forced using withheld testing data, with comparison to ERA5 and baseline model. Initialized at 7:00 UTC on June 1, 2016 at 35.5°N , 260.0°W . Residual s_t and r_t tendencies have been modified by subtracting vertical advective tendencies diagnosed by centered differencing, leaving only the diabatic contributions.

Figure 5.5: Mean bias profiles for s_l and r_t as a function of simulation time, averaged for each timestep across all 7-day simulations for the 2016 Southern Great Plains.

systematic drift in the baseline simulations away from the analysis profiles (Figure 5.5), this is not a main contributor to error in the baseline model. If we correct each sample by the mean bias for its timestep, the baseline error increases by less than 0.05.

Having seen an example integration over the SGP, we statistically evaluate performance on the testing year using the second half of the 7-day simulations in Table 5.1. The performance of MARBLE levels off sooner over this region, as seen in Figure 5.6, but we keep the evaluation period identical for consistency.

Compared to the Northeast Pacific, model performance for thermodynamic quantities is slightly degraded, but still very high. Given the greater amount of variability overall in the region and stronger horizontal advective forcings, this is a positive achievement. Single-column models often have difficulty coming into equilibrium with advected thermodynamic properties, but this is not an issue in MARBLE. This is an advantage of MARBLE being trained in a prognostic setting, while subjected to realistic horizontal advective forcings.

As over the NEP, MARBLE has difficulty predicting sharp vertical gradients of cloud properties, and instead smooths the vertical profiles, resulting in lower performance. This could almost certainly be improved with more attention paid to the neural network structure

Figure 5.6: Fraction of variance explained (R^2) for key quantities as a function of simulation time, averaged for each timestep across all 7-day simulations for the 2016 Southern Great Plains. Note the y-axis begins at 0.5 for clarity.

Table 5.1: MARBLE performance for 2016 Southern Great Plains. Simulations described in Section 4.4. Evaluation is performed over the last 3.5 days of each 7-day simulation. The training mean at each height is subtracted before calculating the squared correlation coefficient R^2 . Baseline values are computed from the baseline model described in Section 4.4.1. Liquid water static energy is rescaled into temperature units by dividing by the heat capacity of dry air at constant pressure.

Quantity	Mean Bias	RMSE	R^2	Baseline R^2
liquid water static energy (s_l/C_{pd})	0.42 K	3.5 K	0.84	0.40
total water mixing ratio (r_t)	0.11 g/kg	1.2 g/kg	0.86	0.40
clear-sky radiative heating rate (R_{cs})	0.014 K/hr	0.033 K/hr	0.96	N/A
vertically-resolved cloud fraction (C)	-0.0011	0.058	0.66	N/A
cloud water mixing ratio (r_c)	-5.1×10^{-4} g/kg	1.9×10^{-2} g/kg	0.62	N/A
rain water mixing ratio (r_{rain})	1.3×10^{-4} g/kg	5.5×10^{-3} g/kg	0.89	N/A
column low cloud fraction (C_{low})	-0.036	0.06	0.66	N/A
surface precipitation (P_s)	0.012 mm/h	0.46 mm/h	0.86	N/A
column cloud water (\mathcal{L})	-0.0021 kg/m ²	0.037 kg/m ²	0.84	N/A

Figure 5.7: Horizontally-resolved mean values and correlation coefficients of key quantities, averaged across the last 3.5 days of 7-day simulations for the 2016 Southern Great Plains.

used to predict these outputs. Here we are concerned mainly with prognostic evolution, and in MARBLE the predicted cloud fraction plays no role in determining tendencies of prognostic variables.

While horizontally-resolved climatology is of lesser importance over the SGP than the NEP, it is encouraging to see that it is also well-represented in this region (Figure 5.7). MARBLE accurately captures the greater cloud fraction and precipitation towards the north and east sides of the domain. The model is skillful in these diagnostic outputs throughout the domain, as shown in the rightmost column.

Overall, MARBLE does a good job in representing the mean diurnal variability of cloud fraction and precipitation in the SGP (Figures 5.8, 5.9). It produces a reduction in cloudiness during the day, and increased precipitation near dawn and dusk. MARBLE does not represent the peak in surface precipitation seen at 2pm local time. This may be the result of MARBLE underestimating the magnitude of the strongest high-precipitation events, or possibly due to the low frequency of precipitation events in this time interval. There is no precipitation at 2pm more than 85% of the time in the testing dataset. MARBLE also

Figure 5.8: Mean diurnal cycle of cloud fraction and precipitation, averaged across the last 3.5 days of 7-day simulations for the Southern Great Plains in April, May, June, July, and August 2016. Local hour is based on mean longitude over the SGP domain.

underpredicts the magnitude of the peak in cloud fraction in the evening. This bias may be coupled with other evening-time biases, including the lack of a near-surface maximum in air moisture and the over-prediction of the magnitude of the moisture minimum above the boundary layer.

To improve qualitative performance for cloud fraction and precipitation, it may be worthwhile to perform a transformation to the cloud fraction and precipitation outputs so that over the training data, the distribution of predicted values matches ERA5 exactly. This would help rectify the issues of underestimating the magnitude of high precipitation events or full cloud cover events, and the issue of predicting small or negative values of cloud fraction and precipitation when the value should be zero. This is left as a suggestion for future exploration.

Figure 5.9: Mean diurnal cycle of liquid static energy (s_l), total water mixing ratio (r_t), and vertically resolved cloud fraction, averaged as in Figure 5.8. Profiles for s_l and r_t are shown as perturbations from the mean vertical profile over the training dataset. s_l is normalized by heat capacity of dry air at constant pressure (C_{pd}) to have units of degrees Kelvin.

Chapter 6

FUTURE AVENUES AND CONCLUSIONS

This dissertation has introduced diverse concepts from software development and machine learning and applied them to boundary-layer parameterization. We conclude by reflecting on some lessons for moving forward.

6.1 Using Sympl to accelerate model development

In Chapter 2, we introduced the Sympl framework and CliMT toolkit for writing climate models. This framework was used for testing CHOMP prognostically in Chapter 3. Using Python allowed rapid prototyping of the parameterization with online analysis code and plotting. This sped up the development cycle and allowed for rapid testing of model changes. This is mostly a benefit of using Python, rather than a benefit of using Sympl itself. The core benefit of using Sympl in this case was to ensure the model code written was well-documented and modular.

In progressing to MARBLE in Chapter 4, Sympl was not used, but not because Sympl is not useful for this purpose. The code for MARBLE consists entirely of scripts to preprocess ERA5 data and scripts to use the machine learning library Keras to train MARBLE. The model training scripts save model weights and also produce evaluation runs on testing data, in a way that is guaranteed to be consistent with the training method. These evaluation runs are then evaluated directly by Python scripts.

MARBLE has since been re-written as a Sympl component, available at <https://github.com/mcgibbon/marble/>. This will allow other researchers to more readily understand and use the parameterization. It will also simplify re-implementation of the MARBLE in other languages, by way of documentation. In terms of incorporating MARBLE into other models,

several difficulties remain that are scientific in nature. For example, the vertical grid used by MARBLE is somewhat atypical and must be interpolated to and from, the vertical domain stops above the boundary layer, and the model performs vertical mean advection but not horizontal advection.

6.2 *Extending MARBLE to cover the globe*

Having seen MARBLE work well in two distinct climatological regions, there is hope that this approach could be expanded to work in a global model. The main issues that remain in reaching that point are (1) incorporating prognostic momentum equations into the model, (2) incorporating communication between columns in the horizontal, and (3) training on a dataset that is much larger than can fit in memory. When discussing memory considerations, we should also consider how to set up the vertical representation of variability in the model. Here we discuss these issues one by one and lay out a path forward for MARBLE.

6.2.1 Horizontal Communication

Since horizontal momentum plays no role in MARBLE other than in determining horizontal advective fluxes, issues (1) and (2) must be considered together. An additional point to (1) is that latent and sensible heat fluxes need to be diagnosed rather than prescribed, which can be done once we have prognostic surface velocity and surface energy budget. In training MARBLE, we decided to fold vertical mean advection into the machine learning component, but this is unlikely to be relevant for horizontal advection. In the atmosphere and in particular in the marine boundary layer, vertical mean advection is often in balance with subgrid-scale vertical advection. To avoid large errors when taking the difference between two large terms, it is ideal to predict the sum of that balance instead of an individual term. In addition, the low-dimensional representation of the vertical column in MARBLE means explicit vertical advection using centered differencing results in large numerical errors. This is likely part of the reason we were unable to train a neural network that incorporated explicit vertical advection.

By contrast, it is not common practice to use subgrid parameterizations for horizontal advective fluxes in the atmosphere, owing to the relative magnitudes of mean advective contribution versus subgrid advection in the horizontal. Instead we can rely solely on the dynamical core to determine horizontal advective fluxes. But can we use the dynamical core to determine vertical mean fluxes of horizontal momentum? At the least, if the dynamical core is relied upon for this, the vertical mean momentum flux should likely be provided as an input for MARBLE to determine its subgrid flux.

To do this, there are two possible routes. One is, like before, to predetermine the "forced" vertical mean momentum flux and horizontal advective fluxes and create a single-column training dataset. This has the benefit that it is straightforward to train and configure - this has already been done for MARBLE. It should likely be done as a first pass. This has the downside that when MARBLE is actually used in three dimensions, there will be feedback between MARBLE's momentum flux and the advective forcings, which cannot be learned from this "forced" training process. A possible way around this is to use a first-pass trained model to produce a set of prognostic simulations, and use the advective forcings from the first-pass model to train a second model, iterating the training process until convergence. This is not guaranteed to work, but it may possibly work.

The other route is to incorporate the dynamical core into the machine learning model. We attempted this to some degree in MARBLE by putting centered differenced vertical advection explicitly into the neural network. It only deteriorated performance, but this may be due to centered differencing being a poor choice for the low-dimensional representation we used. As we will discuss shortly, a low-dimensional representation is not necessary, and a more accurate vertical and horizontal advection scheme could be incorporated into the network.

It does however require that the advection scheme be coded in a machine learning library, in a way that is differentiable. It could not use upwind schemes, limiters, or iterative solvers. This also requires that the network be written over the globe, or at least a sizeable fraction of it, and that the entire domain worth of training data be put into memory at a time.

Grid stretching becomes an issue when calculating any kind of horizontal derivatives in the network, and it would be a challenge, though not necessarily impossible, to incorporate a grid with irregularities, such as a cubed-sphere grid, into the network.

6.2.2 Using Larger Datasets

In terms of issue (3) regarding memory considerations, we mentioned a low-dimensional vertical representation is not necessarily required. This was done mainly to fit the training dataset into memory, which cannot be done at all if training a global model. We discuss below how to train a model in such a scenario. It should be possible to train a network that takes as input and output the full vertical column on a height or pressure grid.

One benefit that a low-dimensional representation provides is in speeding up the training of the network and avoiding overfitting. However, this can be done without the use of principal components, within the context of a neural network. We would suggest attempting to train a model with and without dimensionality reduction, and using the model that performs better on validation data. This dimensionality reduction is achieved by first training an autoencoder neural network that returns its inputs but contains fewer internal neurons than the number of inputs. Once trained, the encoder portion of that network is then attached to the much wider neural network that is then trained to compute the outputs of MARBLE. We did not use this approach because it requires transferring the entire vertical column into the GPU for training.

So when training on a much larger dataset, how do we train the model without it fitting on the GPU or even in memory? On a practical level, this is done simply by writing a `Sequence` object in Keras, as documented at <https://keras.io/utils/#sequence>. The package will handle the rest. This will significantly slow down training as the data is re-read from disk and re-transferred between memory and the GPU. To overcome this, one might train the model on multiple GPUs in parallel. This again can be done easily in Keras, with the `multi_gpu_model` object documented at https://keras.io/utils/#multi_gpu_model. We strongly recommend doing so, as a faster training cycle results in errors being found and

corrected more quickly.

6.2.3 *Fundamental Limitations*

In the end, while MARBLE grants us significant improvements over forecast models, it can only be trusted within the range of its training data. Namely, it is limited by the observational record. It would be expected to under-predict any kind of climate changes due to increased CO₂, even once it is modified to take CO₂ as an input in some fashion (currently it does not, including through longwave radiation, which it predicts itself). When trained on reanalysis data, MARBLE is likely strongest in a weather forecasting setting, where it can be trained for example on the most recent decade of reanalysis.

One could instead apply the approach for MARBLE to emulate a high-resolution model, but then we are still limited by the performance of the high-resolution model. It could then grant the benefit of being able to run the high-resolution model on a bounding subset of conditions, from which the machine learning model could interpolate (rather than extrapolate). The use of machine learning emulation of high-resolution models underscores the importance in developing and testing high-resolution models. At a resolution that might otherwise be cost-prohibitive for most researchers to use, one could use a much lower resolution trained model that produces similar results to the high-resolution model.

6.3 *What would it take to make CHOMP work?*

As shown in Brenowitz and Bretherton [8] and Chapter 4, neural networks can be used to train stable models by optimizing their output over the course of many timesteps. When using this approach, unstable models are penalized greatly as the error they produce is accumulated over the many timesteps being optimized.

One may have success creating a HOC parameterization using this approach. In essence, MARBLE is a HOC parameterization that closes the equations at first-order. The main difficulty for higher-order closure is in obtaining a training dataset with reliable higher-order moments that is sufficiently large to train the model. For a global parameterization used

for predicting climate changes, this would involve something akin to running a global cloud resolving model or large-eddy simulation for several years of simulation time.

Once this large dataset is obtained, one must explicitly code the higher-order moment equations in a neural network framework like Keras, creating a MARBLE-like model that trains over many time steps. The representation of vertical derivatives must be continuous and differentiable. The outputs of the model should likely be the tendencies of some set of higher-order moments (such as the second order moments), as is done in MARBLE for mean values. The loss function should be constructed in such a way that gives weighting proportional to the importance of the outputs, namely giving more weighting to mean values than to second-order moments. Including the tendency itself as a term in the loss function may improve training performance as a "hint" for the optimizer towards the correct tendency, but its weighting should be significantly less than the weighting for the terms the tendency is being added to. This is because one expects those tendencies to contain numerical error, as we found in developing CHOMP, and also physical processes that may be unnecessary for long-term prognostic performance and detrimental to numerical stability.

6.4 Concluding remarks

In this dissertation we have shown how software development best practices and techniques from machine learning can be applied to atmospheric parameterization development. Machine learning models show promise in learning better subgrid representations from observations, suggesting improvements to reanalysis products may yield improvements in forecast skill once parameterizations like MARBLE are used in forecast models.

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VITA

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He continued his education at the University of Toronto to study Physics, where he received an Honors Bachelor of Science in 2014. At various times during his stay at the University of Toronto he had the pleasure of performing research under Doctors Natalia Krasnopolskaia, Stephen Morris, and Paul Kushner. He also served as a Residential Don at Morrison Hall in University College, and as a summer customer service employee at the CN Tower.

Following this, Jeremy completed his Masters and Doctoral studies at the University of Washington under the supervision of Dr. Christopher Bretherton. There he gave departmental tutorials on Python with fellow graduate student Andre Perkins, served as a representative of graduate students on the Graduate and Professional Student Senate and as a departmental Graduate Student Representative (GSR), and established the departmental Diversity and Inclusion Group with fellow GSR Judy Twedt. Jeremy is grateful to Chris both for suggesting a Masters research project which gave him a solid foundation for understanding atmospheric processes in a modeling framework, and for allowing him to explore his own ideas applying concepts from software development and machine learning in his doctoral research.